

**Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting
women's contribution to the history of societies**

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1. Introduction

The project HerStory aims to challenge the narrative that the field of history is male dominated by highlighting women's presence and contributions throughout history. The project aims to fill the gap of missing information about women's role in shaping society, as mainstream literature on women's history is limited and their contributions are often overlooked.

The research was conducted around 8 European cities, in 8 European countries involving 9 European institutions. This document has been developed through the common effort of organisations and institutions from: Salamanca/Spain (GRIAL Research Group, University of Salamanca), Martinique/France (D' Antilles et D' Ailleurs), Nicosia/Cyprus (The Advisory Centre for the Support of the Family – SYKESO and Centre for Social Innovation – CSI Cyprus), Athens/Greece (Kyttaro Enallaktikon Anazitiseon Neon – KEAN), Sofia/Bulgaria (Infinite Opportunities Association – IOA), Velenje/Slovenia (Ljudska univerza Velenje – LUV), Vilnius/Lithuania (Diversity Development Group – DDG), Lecco/Italy (Specchio Magico Cooperativa Sociale Onlus).

Through a bottom-up research approach and the development of local multi-stakeholder networks, the consortium manages to enhance the visibility of women in history and challenge the field of history in a gender perspective way. During this research the consortium detected statues and historical areas that represent female figures in history, thus raising awareness about their contribution.

The desk research “Mapping the women’s footprint on local histories” aims to investigate women’s triumphs and normalise the success of women through the publicity of women’s statues and monuments, street names, and historical places related to women’s presence in society. In this way, any historical misconceptions and misrepresentations can be addressed towards gender equality. The development of a European report on this specific field can fill the gap that exists in the history of European cities.

A European report is important in order to fill the gap of missing information regarding women’s footprint in history. Such reports can contribute to changing the frame and the reflection of conclusive male patterns’ impact on people. The outcomes of the research can

provide knowledge and inspiration to young people and stakeholders around Europe. Finally, the results of the research will work as a source of information for the development of the transnational map where the visitors will be able to find remarkable places regarding women in history in all partner cities of the consortium.

2. Methodology

The consortium followed a well-structured methodology to develop the European Report and the Methods Manual.

Firstly, desk research was followed by the 9 partners at a national level to investigate women's triumphs and equal gender visibility in each partner city. Each partner reviewed publications such as articles, scientific research, reports, historical documents, historical books, newspaper articles, publications on city tours, etc. In this way, the quality of the desk research provided information on local-level women's footprint in history, along with the effect of structural constraints regarding gender equality in each partner country.

Secondly, partners developed focus groups with stakeholders and young people. The aim of the focus groups with stakeholders was to summarize the needs orientation while reporting best practices, methods, and tools to highlight women's marks in local history. Each partner involved experts such as historians, people from women's organisations, tour guides, academics and researchers in gender, history, architecture, etc. In this way, fruitful results in regard with the current state of knowledge of female remarkable history figures in each city, were pointed out.

Also, a focus group with young people took place. The aim of the focus group with young people was to report their knowledge regarding women's footprint on their local history and suggest methods to be used in the development of the transnational HerStory map. The feedback of young people will enhance the quality of the HerStory map since the consortium managed to detect attractive and inspirational was to address the needs of young people in order to engage them through the life plan of the HerStory project.

The analysing of the results of the desk research, and the results of the Focus Groups with stakeholders and young people combine the content of 9 National Reports and define the quality of the European Report and the Methods Manual.

3. Findings on Desk Research at transnational level

3.1. Spain

In Spain, since the promulgation of the Spanish Constitution in 1978, equality between women and men has been affirmed in Spain. Almost a decade later, in 1987, the Women's Institute was created to promote and foster the conditions that would enable social equality of both sexes and the participation of women in political, cultural, economic and social life¹.

However, the incorporation of the gender perspective in Spain came about as a result of Organic Law 3/2007 of 22 March 2007, which proposed the prevention of discriminatory behaviour and the provision of active policies to make the principle of equality effective in the different areas of social, cultural and artistic reality in which inequality could be generated and perpetuated, and to make equality between women and men effective². With the implementation of this Organic Law 3/2007, a significant step was taken towards making knowledge of the reality and potential inequalities between men and women more visible, paving the way for the incorporation of the gender perspective in statistics and studies mentioned in Article 20, which states that it must contribute to the recognition and valuation of women's work and avoid the negative stereotyping of certain groups of women. However, although the need to incorporate the gender perspective in statistics and studies is recognised, the truth is that there is very little literature on the subject in Spain, and there is still a long way to go to incorporate the gender perspective in a cross-cutting manner¹. At the autonomous community level, Castilla y León's Statute establishes, in Article 70.1.11, the exclusive competence of the independent community in promoting equal treatment and opportunities between women and men.

¹ Inmujeres, « Origins of the Women's Institute », 2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.inmujeres.gob.es/actualidad/noticias/2022/OCTUBRE/indiceuropeoigualdad.htm>.

² BOE, «Ley Orgánica 3/2007, de 22 de marzo, for the effective equality of women and men. », núm. 71, mar. 2007. Retrieved from: <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2007-6115>

Despite the progress that has been seen in the creation of laws and institutions that regulate gender equality, there are still challenges in various work sectors, including equal salaries, equality plans in companies, equality on boards of directors, equality in birth permits ³.

3.1.1. Gender representation in History in Spain

Men have always been the protagonists of the different studies in many disciplines, from the great cultural, social, political and economic revolutions, with great invisibility towards the contribution of women in the different disciplines and fields of knowledge; history, literature, philosophy, art, social sciences, engineering, this has consequently resulted in literary, philosophical, artistic, economist and scientific canons being biased in favour of men ⁴.

Woysner (2002) ⁵ mentions that in many existing curriculum frameworks, women's history content is added to an already full plate. It can be seen as counterproductive, as women are in danger of being lost when attempting to be inclusive within a thematic approach. Women are subsumed under broad themes, but in the process many references to women are omitted so that they appear to be effectively excluded, in any case, women's history remains in a precarious position.

The inclusion of gender diversity is relevant and challenging for schools and teaching. In recent years there has been interest in the presence/absence of women in curricula, syllabi and textbooks, and also in teachers' work on including the invisible in history teaching in particular ⁶. Some authors, such as Scott (2008) ⁷, argue that history has been written to exclude women and gender studies due to patriarchal culture.

Hence the importance of making women visible on an equal footing to men's actions, highlighting repression, marginalisation, absence and gender hierarchies ⁶, ⁸. Scott (2008)

³ UOC, «Challenges of gender equality in Spain», 2018. Retrieved from: <https://fp.uoc.fje.edu/blog/retos-de-la-igualdad-de-genero-en-espana/>.

⁴ C. García, « Women and history. Questioning invisibility and becoming visible », *Historical processes. Revista de Historia y Ciencias Sociales*, n.º 29, 2016.

⁵ C. Woysner, «Political History as Women's History: Toward a More Inclusive Curriculum», *Theory & Research in Social Education*, vol. 30, n.º 3, pp. 354-380, jul. 2002, doi: 10.1080/00933104.2002.10473201.

⁶ J. Marolla, « The inclusion of women in history classes: possibilities and limitations from the conceptions of Chilean students », *Rev. Colomb. Educ.*, vol. 1, n.º 77, may 2019, doi: 10.17227/rce.num77-6549.

⁷ J. W. Scott, *Genre and history. Mexico*. Fondo de Cultura Económica, 2008.

⁸ M. Crocco, «Caught between Invisibility and Stereotyping: Teaching the Novel Shabanu», *Social Education*, vol. 70, n.º 4, pp. 178-182, 2006

recognises the importance of rescuing women's actions in constructing historical narratives; however, she argues that reflection should be oriented towards women's empowerment in the face of gender inequalities in history teaching⁵. Fernández (2006)⁹ agrees that including women could provoke reflection on who have been the protagonists of history. Subirats & Anguita, (2021)¹⁰ affirm the urgency of building a teaching that promotes gender diversity and constructing a co-educational perspective. To do so, it is necessary to reinterpret history and establish a space where the role played by women and people who have been silenced by a history that has given prominence to men with power over others is made evident⁶.

3.2. France (Martinique)

Martinique is a French territorial collectivity located in the Antilles (Caribbean region), between the English-speaking islands of Dominica and Saint Lucia. From the 17th to the 19th century, it was the site of the enslavement of West Africans and their descendants. The abolition of slavery in Martinique occurred on May 22, 1848, following the French government's decision to abolish slavery in all French colonies. After emancipation, former slaves in Martinique faced various challenges as they sought to build new lives and improve their socio-economic conditions. That's why the question of gender equality and gender representation was not the principal concern for the people of Martinique, comparing to Metropolitan France where feminist mobilization was already well underway in 1848. So, it's only recently that these issues have taken an important place in Martinique.

Today, it's observed that in Martinique, many gender inequalities persist. The island's history but also the structural constraints can have significant effects on the status, opportunities, and rights of women, contributing to gender inequality. These constraints refer to the social norms, policies, laws, and institutionalized practices that perpetuate gender inequalities.

One of the first effects of these constraints is an unequal division of labor between men and women that persists in Martinique. During the colonial period, women in Martinique were

⁹ A. Fernández, << La construcción de identidad desde la perspectiva de Género>>, *Íber*, vol. 47, pp. 33-44.

¹⁰ M. Subirats y R. Anguita, *Educating women: the construction of the coeducational perspective. in equality*, no. n° 7. Valladolid: Ediciones Universidad de Valladolid, 2021.

largely excluded from positions of power and authority. The dominant patriarchal system limited their participation in public life and confined them to domestic and reproductive roles.

Today, although women are generally more highly educated than men, they are more often unemployed with the same level of qualifications. They are also certain sectors or industries dominated by one gender. Women are often concentrated in lower-paying and less valued sectors, while men dominate higher-paying positions and leadership within companies (managers, CEOs, senior executives, business owners). This occupational segregation contributes to limited career advancement opportunities but also income disparities. In fact, for the same job, women in Martinique earn more than 2000 euros less a year than men . This gender wage gap is also reinforced by other economic disparities between women and men. Women in Martinique may face obstacles in accessing economic resources such as credit, land ownership, or entrepreneurship opportunities and hinder women's economic independence and autonomy.

Structural constraints can also impede women's political participation and representation. In Martinique, women are underrepresented in political spheres, both at the local and national levels, due to obstacles such as sexist biases, discriminatory practices, and limited access to political networks and resources. And even if the representation of women among elected representatives is improving, few hold positions of responsibility. Consequently, women are often marginalized in political decision-making, limiting their ability to influence policies and advocate for gender equality issues.

Today, only five women are mayors and nine are first deputies in Martinique's thirty-four communes. None presides over the three agglomeration communities, and only one is first vice-president . However, the last years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of women's participation in decision-making processes. Efforts have been made to increase women's representation in politics and ensure that their voices are heard in policymaking and governance.

These constraints can also contribute to higher rates of gender-based violence against women. Norms and attitudes that perpetuate gender inequalities can normalize and tolerate certain forms of violence against women and reinforce abusive behaviors. This is a significant

issue in Martinique, where physical and psychological violence against women is very prevalent.

All the structural constraints are reinforced by cultural norms and stereotypes deeply ingrained in society (it's very visible in Martinique) that perpetuate traditional gender roles and expectations. This can exert social pressures on women to conform to certain standards of beauty, behavior, and social roles, restricting their autonomy and freedom of choice in various areas of life, including education, employment, and decision-making.

By addressing these structural constraints and promoting gender equality, Martinique can work towards creating a more inclusive and equitable society for all.

3.2.1. Gender representation in history in Martinique

Gender representation in Martinique's history has often been biased and unequal, with women's contributions and experiences marginalized or neglected. The historical narrative has mainly focused on the achievements and perspectives of men, while women's voices and roles have been largely ignored. This is the case in France, but even more in Martinique.

In recent years, efforts have been made to discover and highlight the important contributions of women in shaping the history of Martinique. A more balanced gender representation in crucial areas such as history is essential because the underrepresentation of women in history can lead to a biased and incomplete view of the past, primarily highlighting male achievements and perpetuating gender inequalities in society. A fair representation of both women and men in history allows for the recognition of the contributions and achievements of Martinican women who have played significant roles in the development of society, culture, and social movements.

To achieve this goal, it is crucial to promote and support inclusive historical research that highlights the role of women in various aspects of Martinican society. This also includes disseminating this knowledge through education, media, publications, and other means so that current and future generations can have a better understanding of history in all its diversity and enrichment through women's contributions.

By including female perspectives in the history of Martinique, a better understanding of the impact of women can be achieved. It also promotes the identification of role models for future generations, demonstrating that women have always been active and influential in shaping the region's history.

3.3. Cyprus

Despite Cyprus's legal framework on gender equality, political, socioeconomic, and cultural obstacles to women's development still exist in Cyprus. These obstacles prevent women from achieving their full potential. Gender stereotypes are well-rooted in the Cypriot society. Hence, society expects from women and men to behave in a specific way. Society has different expectations from women and men. Women are expected to be mothers and wives more than to be present in the political and social spectrum. Thus, the societal pressure on responding to the gender characteristics put barriers to women. This is happening, in regard to the absence of governmental policies that supports parenthood also. Gender stereotypes and gender inequality can be harmful from both genders.

Gender equality has not been a priority in Cyprus for a very long time, and there is no significant political consensus about gender equality policy. Male models dominate decision-making in all social and political structures and processes, including government and political parties, parliament, the judiciary, the economy, and the mass media, in addition to a lack of gender balance in almost all spheres of life and ineffective implementation and monitoring mechanisms.

The European Institute for Gender Equality's statistics for the 2022 index reveals that gender equality has an average percentage of 68.6% at the EU level and Cyprus reached 57.3%, which means that Cyprus is in the 7th position from the bottom. Only 25% of ministers in Cyprus are female, with 75% being men (2023). Only 14.3% of MEPs are women, compared to 85.7% of men in the parliament. The equivalent statistic for female MEPs at the European level is 33%. Women's participation in political and social life in Cyprus is only 30%. The average monthly earnings of female employees in Cyprus for the 4th quarter of 2022 are €2, 024 while those of men are €2, 408. Women (81%) are the ones who take care of children and the household.

Additionally, it is worth mentioning that incidents of gender and domestic violence have exceeded 5 500 in the last two years.

These statistics reflect the gender inequality in Cyprus and thus, the underrepresentation of women in the public space. In addition to that the stereotypical structure of the private sector still exists. Statistics on the private sector of life reveal that women are primarily accountable for domestic responsibilities such as cooking, cleaning, and caring for the family's most vulnerable members. This demonstrates how women dominate the personal arena of life while simultaneously staying out of politics and the public sphere. These contentious facts mostly reflect the long-standing gender traditions of the countries in which female figures confront as a caregiver and as a mother in order to address the given characteristics in each gender.

3.3.1. Gender representation in history in Cyprus

Gender norms in Cyprus were well established and men and women were expected to act and behave under specific characteristics and attitudes which were considered as acceptable in the Cypriot society. Women who want to participate in politics and public life encounter a wide range of complex difficulties.

The reasons for gender inequalities and gender misrepresentation in all aspects of life are multifaceted, systemic, and structural. To understand the reality of the Cypriot society, it is crucial to point out some historical conditions of the Cypriot society's development.

Women in Cyprus face different experiences and thus, their lives are far different from men's lives and therefore, women have different needs. Especially in Cyprus in which an ethnic conflict has affected the history of the island (The Cyprus problem), women have been mobilized in the dominant patriarchal and militaristic environment. Power relations were reflected also in gender relations. This interaction affected the whole structure of masculinity and femininity in the Cypriot society through ages. Historical, socio-economic, and cultural conditions affected real life experience of gender representation in Cyprus.

Prior to Cyprus's independence, women's roles were limited to the household, and only those who were socially and economically advantaged had access to education. Furthermore, in Cyprus, back in the time, positions of employment were divided by gender between males

and females. Gender norms were also represented in the labour market, with sectors such as the “women’s sectors” and the “male-dominant sectors”. That means that labour sectors that were considered as female and/or male sectors of the labour market and thus, labour sectors were representing gender characteristics and attitudes.

Therefore, Cypriot women were either unpaid housewives or nurses, secretaries, teachers, or employed in agriculture and factories. And of course, women were expected to give up their career once they were getting married and/or having children and family. This is something that was happening because women were responsible to keep up with everything in the household and they were also responsible for the children’s nurture. However, women were not absent from the Cypriot public sphere, historically, culturally, and socially wise. Some of the great Cypriot women’s remarkable examples will be presented in the National Report of Cyprus, later in this document.

In order to change gender inequalities in both the private sector, such as the family and the home, and the public sector, such as male-dominated politics and the employment sectors, feminists challenged these socially constructed dichotomies and started to promote the idea that these characteristics are a result of historical, cultural, and patriarchal structures. These goals came across with oriented strategies and struggles on legal and cultural changes.

3.3.2. Gender representation in history in Nicosia

The historical tapestry of Nicosia, Cyprus, boasts a nuanced narrative interwoven with the indelible marks left by women, often regrettably overshadowed by historical oversight. Institutions such as the Leventis Municipal Museum of Nicosia and the Cyprus Museum are entrusted with the responsibility of portraying the city's multifaceted history. However, these depictions frequently marginalize the pivotal role women have played. This exploration seeks to undertake a critical analysis of the portrayal of women's contributions within the historical and socio-political backdrop of Nicosia. By delving into artistic, political, and social spheres, this investigation underscores the necessity of revealing and recognizing the substantial yet frequently marginalized role of women in the annals of Nicosia's history.

Artistic Endeavors and Cultural Enrichment: The artistic landscape of Nicosia stands as a testament to the broader patterns of gender dynamics in Cyprus, revealing persistent gender

inequalities. Figures such as Glyn Hughes, a British-Cypriot painter, bear witness to women's instrumental involvement in enriching the city's cultural milieu. However, their role has often been downplayed within the narratives presented by institutions like the Leventis Municipal Museum and the Cyprus Museum. An exploration of Hughes' contributions illuminates the broader significance of women's contributions to the arts in Nicosia, urging a more comprehensive representation of their endeavours in cultural narratives.

Gender and Leadership in Politics and Business: Despite advancements in women's education, Nicosia, much like Cyprus at large, remains embroiled in a gendered paradox within politics and business domains. A glass ceiling, impervious to educational attainment, prevails, thereby impeding women's ascendancy to leadership positions. Noteworthy exceptions, such as Stella Kyriakides, the former European Commissioner for Health and Food Safety, provide glimpses of progress. However, the overall representation of women in higher echelons remains constrained. A meticulous inquiry into this conundrum uncovers systemic obstacles that hinder women's progress in domains marked by unequal gender distribution.

Gender Disparities in Political Representation: The political landscape of Nicosia epitomizes the disparities between genders, with men constituting a notable 76% of political representation, leaving women at a mere 24%. Even with the historic appointment of Mrs. Annita Dimitriou as the first female president of the parliament, and despite the fact that the capital of Cyprus, Nicosia, in the previous years had a female mayor, Mrs. Eleni Mavrou, the scales remain tipped in favour of men. A comprehensive understanding of gender dynamics necessitates an exploration beyond institutions, where women's presence reverberates through the very streets of Nicosia. Many thoroughfares, such as Xanthi Zenierou Street, Kleovoulou Street, and Eleni Vakondiou Street, serve as reminders of women's enduring influence and resilience.

Historical Vanguard: Mrs. Polyxeni Loizias: Mrs. Polyxeni Loizias, an esteemed figure in Nicosia's history, emerges as a pioneering feminist, educator, writer, and activist. Her establishment of the "Union of Greek Women," the inaugural women's gym "The Palladion," and the first women's magazine marked a radical departure from societal norms, setting the groundwork for women's emancipation across Cyprus. Loizias' transformative initiatives

underscore the historical underpinnings of women's empowerment in Nicosia, transcending the limitations of traditional gender roles.

Monuments and the Gendered Narrative: The historical underrepresentation of women becomes poignantly evident when examining the commemorative landscape of Nicosia. While monuments and statues perpetuate male-centred narratives, women's invaluable contributions often remain obscured. A dearth of monuments acknowledging women's involvement in liberation struggles and other historical milestones perpetuates this gendered disparity. The review underscores the need for an inclusive commemorative landscape that faithfully reflects the diverse and vital roles women have played in shaping Nicosia's history.

3.4. Greece

The current structural constraints regarding gender equality in Greece are highly associated to the ideological commitment of Greeks to the institution of the family, which is very high by EU standards, but also to the social effects of the economic crisis of 2009 that Greece is still dealing with its consequences.

In Greece, the concept of family is traditionally understood in a broader context that encompasses kinship ties and plays a central role in providing care and support. Within this framework, the family is responsible for various forms of caregiving, including childcare, care for adults, accommodation, and emotional support. Since the 1980s, Greece has undergone significant changes in terms of gender roles and the structure of the family, due to migration to urban centers. As people moved away from their extended family networks in rural areas, the pattern of the nuclear family became more prevalent. This shift from extended to nuclear family structures brought about changes in family dynamics and a greater emphasis on individual needs, aspirations, and autonomy within the family context. These changes were marked by feminist movements that led to law reforms, such as the Family Law reform of 1983, which included a lot of the claims of women's associations (Papadopoulos, 1998. Davaki, 2001)¹¹.

¹¹ Papadopoulos, T. N. (2002). Greek family policy from a comparative perspective. In *Women, work and the family in Europe* (pp. 65-75). Routledge; Davaki, K. (2001). *Women in the Labour Market and the Family: Policies in Germany and Greece*. Unpublished PhD Thesis. Canterbury, University of Kent.

Despite all these shifts and the steps toward gender equality, it seems that traditional family values continue to be important for many Greeks. The concept of family still extends beyond the nuclear unit to include extended family members and close kin. Greek families tend to have strong bonds and maintain close relationships, with a focus on mutual support, care, and collective well-being. This fact impacts gender equality and the sustainment of traditional gender roles. Thus, women may take on more domestic and caregiving responsibilities while men focus on work and providing for the family. However, there is an increasing trend towards more egalitarian gender roles, with shared household tasks and childcare responsibilities.

The gender wage gap in Greece has been a persistent issue, as highlighted by various studies and data. The ratio of female to male earnings had declined from about 35% in the 1970s to roughly 25-30% in the 1990s. Nevertheless, the pay gap between women and men in Greece in 2010 was still 22% (European Commission, 2012)¹².

Historically, women have been underrepresented in various sectors of Greek society, including politics, corporate leadership, and certain professions. In terms of politics, Greece had made some progress in increasing the representation of women in the parliament and government. In the 2019 legislative election, a record number of women were elected to the Hellenic Parliament, accounting for about 18% of the seats. This was a significant improvement compared to previous years, but it still indicated that women were not yet equally represented.

Balancing work and family responsibilities remains a challenge for many Greek women. Juggling professional aspirations with household duties and caregiving can be demanding. However, there is a growing recognition of the importance of work-life balance, and discussions around policies to support women in managing these responsibilities are gaining attention.

The financial crisis and the economic downturn that Greece faced from 2009 until 2016, led to a broad deregulation of employment, including the relaxation of collective agreements and

¹² Greek Ombudsman (2012). Gender and Labour Relations Annual Report [in Greek]. Athens, Greek Ombudsman

enforced reduction in the minimum wage, severe cuts in pensions, as well as benefits and subsidies. All these changes affected primarily women, according to the unemployment records of 2013. Nevertheless, part-time work is not fully included in the statistical data since a substantial part of it is hidden within the dark area of the flourishing informal economy. Many women do not appear in the official statistics, as they are either paid cash in hand or do piece work or are unofficially employed in family enterprises (Nikolakopoulou-Stefanou, 1994).

Furthermore, austerity has also intensified issues of discrimination against women in the labour market. Stereotyping seems to be well-grounded in a number of male-dominated sectors (e.g. police, the army), but also in the education, public administration and health services sectors and has been impeding promotion and professional development of women disproportionately. It has become quite common that young women are often asked not to start a family if they are to get a job in the private sector. In other cases, maternity leave intervals were not taken into consideration as periods of service in cases of promotion in the education sector. Discrimination has been also manifested through the reduction in pay and benefits during periods of maternity leave or sick leave in the light of oncoming pregnancy, although legislation is supposed to prevent discrimination of this sort in the public sector (Greek Ombudsman, 2012).

3.4.1. Gender representation in history in Greece

In the history of Greece, gender representation was heavily influenced by societal norms, which were rooted in patriarchal structures. Ancient Greek society was predominantly male dominated, and women's roles were generally confined to the household and family matters. Of course, there were exceptions and variations across different regions and time periods in Greek history. For instance, Spartan women had more freedom and were involved in physical training and some public activities due to the unique social structure of Sparta. Nevertheless, women's role in Greek society didn't change much until the end of the 19th century, when feminist movements began.

As historical records mainly come from male authors, the perspective on women's roles in Greek society is limited and biased. While historical works on women and gender began to

appear in the 19th century, it was not until the feminist movement of the 1970s and 1980s that a systematic analysis of gender practices and representations took place. These studies aimed to shed light on the experiences, struggles, and achievements of women throughout history, with a particular emphasis on the women's movement. This turn to history allowed to show that the oppression of women is a social product and therefore can be challenged and reversed.

The 1980s at the same time witnessed the emergence of “new history” that was dealing with issues such as the extent of industrialisation of Greece. This history paradigm prioritized the study of the state, economic and social development and social stratification, but gender appeared to be of secondary importance. The rise of this approach led to the marginalisation of gender in Greek Universities, as it seemed to disrupt the “new historical narrative” that the state was trying to build after the Greek Junta of 1967.

This situation seems to change only in the beginning of 2000s when more and more dissertations about gender are published in Greek Universities. Also, a lot of chapters dedicated to gender history have been appearing in general historical works. Greek Universities created post-graduate programmes about gender in an anthropological and historical approach (Papadogiannis, 2017. Avdela, 2010)¹³. Although a lot of academics support that gender still has a marginal position in Greek history, some others claim that since the late 1990s there is “a dynamic process of diffusion of women’s and gender’s history in Greek historiographical production as a whole” (Fournaraki & Yannitsiotis, 2013)¹⁴

3.4.2. Gender representation in history in Athens

Throughout the history of Athens, gender representation was also deeply influenced by patriarchy and the general perception of keeping women in domestic roles and for raising

¹³ Papadogiannis, N. (2017). Gender in modern Greek historiography. *Historein*. A review of the past and other stories; Avdela, E. (2010), Η ιστορία του φύλου στην Ελλάδα. Από τη διαταραχή στην ενσωμάτωση [Gender history in Greece: From subversion to incorporation], in Φύλο και κοινωνικές

¹⁴ Fournaraki, E., & Yannitsiotis, Y. (2013). Three decades of women's and gender history in Greece: an account. *Aspasia*, 7, 162

children. While there were some variations in different time periods, certain patterns can be observed regarding the roles and status of women in Athenian society.

For example, in ancient Athens, women were excluded from participating in politics and holding public office. During the Roman or Byzantine period women's status remained generally unchanged. In the 19th and 20th centuries, Athens, like many other cities, experienced social and political changes that affected gender roles. Women's rights movements emerged, advocating for equality, suffrage, and broader participation in public life. In 1954, women in Greece gained the right to vote and being voted and their legal status improved gradually.

3.5. Bulgaria

Bulgaria is among the countries that has been making progress in the field of gender equality, but there are still significant challenges to overcome on a national level. With 60.7 out of 100 points, Bulgaria ranks 18th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index. Its score is 7.9 points below the EU's average score. Our desk research showed that in recent years, Bulgaria has made efforts to address gender equality in various areas such as education, employment, and political representation, however, gender disparities persist in some key areas, and traditional gender roles and stereotypes continue to influence society.

Education has played a crucial role in promoting gender equality and empowering women in the country. Women have equal access to education and are well-represented in various fields of study, including STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics). Bulgaria is even a leader among EU countries when it comes to women studying and working in ICT with, respectively, 34.4% and 27.7% of all tech-related students and employees. Women's participation in the **labour market** is relatively high in Bulgaria. However, they often face challenges related to the gender pay gap and underrepresentation in leadership positions. Women tend to be concentrated in certain sectors, while others, particularly high-level managerial roles, remain predominantly occupied by men. The gender pay gap and workplace discrimination have also been issues that have impacted women's advancement in their careers.

Women's **representation in politics** is relatively low. Although there have been some improvements in recent years, women remain underrepresented in the parliament and other decision-making bodies. During the 45th National Assembly of Bulgaria (elected in April 2021), women accounted for approximately 26% of the total number of members. This was an improvement compared to previous years, but it still fell short of achieving gender parity. Women's underrepresentation in the political sphere can be attributed to various factors, including traditional gender roles, cultural attitudes, and stereotypes, which might discourage women from pursuing political careers.

Violence against women, including domestic violence and sexual harassment, is a significant issue in Bulgaria. Despite efforts to address it through legislation and awareness campaigns, there is still a lot of work to be done to combat gender-based violence effectively. Traditional gender roles and stereotypes persist in Bulgarian society, influencing various aspects of life, including family dynamics and career choices. These stereotypes often perpetuate gender inequalities and limit opportunities for both men and women.

A thorough review on the legislative and policy framework in the country showed that the Bulgarian Constitution of 1991 upholds the principle of equality, ensuring equal rights for all citizens regardless of various factors. The Law on Equality between Women and Men, established in 2016, emphasizes gender mainstreaming, integrating gender equality principles into legislation and policies. Additionally, the Law on Protection from Discrimination, in effect since January 2004, prohibits discrimination, including based on sex.

The National Strategy for Promoting the Equality of Women and Men 2021-2030 is a key policy document for gender equality and is implemented through annual national plans. The current action plan is the Action Plan for the Promotion of Equality Between Women and Men 2021-2022, which utilizes quantitative indicators for monitoring progress and designates specific agencies responsible for data collection.

To make further progress in gender equality, Bulgaria needs to continue addressing the underlying societal norms, cultural attitudes, and institutional barriers that perpetuate gender disparities. This includes implementing and enforcing legislation that protects women's rights, promoting women's participation in decision-making processes, and challenging harmful gender norms through education and awareness campaigns.

Additionally, working towards a more inclusive and equal society should involve engaging men and boys in the conversation on gender equality, as they play a vital role in transforming attitudes and behaviours.

In general, gender representation in Bulgaria, particularly in politics and leadership positions, showed some disparities. Challenges remain, and addressing them requires an **intersectional approach**, including promoting women's education, challenging gender stereotypes, providing support for work- life balance, and implementing measures to promote women's representation in decision-making bodies.

3.5.1. Gender representation in the history in Bulgaria

Women's role before the 20th century was shaped by various social, cultural, and historical factors. The status and experiences of women in this period were influenced by traditional patriarchal norms and the country's historical development. In the traditional Bulgarian society, women typically played central roles within the family and household. They were responsible for domestic duties, childcare, and nurturing the well-being of their families. Education opportunities for women were limited before the 20th century. Formal education was often reserved for boys, while girls received informal education at home, focusing on domestic skills and basic literacy. Women had limited legal and political rights. Inheritance and property rights were often biased towards male heirs, and women did not have the right to vote or participate in public affairs. Customarily, young women were expected to marry and take on the role of a wife and mother at an early age. Although traditional gender roles and societal norms placed restrictions on women's freedom of movement and social interactions, women in Sofia and other cities often engaged in various crafts and trades. They could be found working as weavers, embroiderers, traders, and more.

It's important to note that the experiences of women in Bulgaria before the 20th century were diverse and could vary significantly based on factors such as region, social class, and family circumstances. While traditional gender roles were prevalent, some women found ways to assert their agency and contribute to their communities in various capacities. Over time, social and cultural changes, along with women's movements and advocacy, have gradually led to greater gender equality and expanded opportunities for women.

In the 19th and 20th century Bulgarian women became important participants in the modernized Bulgarian society. Currently, this activity and accomplishments of theirs are almost completely forgotten by the public, and even historical studies present them only as passive witnesses of the events. This is reflected in the collective memory of the nation, where female participation in the creation of national culture is minimized or even completely denied.

3.5.2. Gender representation in the history in Sofia

In Sofia there are very few places of memory, related to the activities and accomplishments of women. In 2017 the Municipal Cultural Institute confirmed that the total number of commemorative signs (or memorial sites) on the territory of the municipality is between 600 and 700. Separately, there are 140 military monuments and 20 military monuments dedicated to foreign troops. Despite these huge numbers, the cultural institute remains unaware of any works of art dedicated to specific women as historical figures. There are 38 memorial plaques dedicated to women, though, of which no more than 30 are still preserved. They denote the homes of famous women writers and poets, artists, actresses and socialites. There are also three tombstones in public places. Unfortunately, most of these memorial locations are damaged and defiled. None of them are indicated on the geographical maps and in the tourist guides of Sofia, they were not created systematically (with a clear criteria and consistency), do not practically affect the collective activity of women (social and professional), are not targeting neither the residents of the city (due to their brevity or unfortunate placement), nor the foreign tourists (due to the lack of bilingual signs and cultural routes), are not present in the modern information environment, nor in various touristic websites.

3.6. Slovenia

The Slovenian Constitution ensures equal human rights and freedoms, prohibiting discrimination based on personal circumstances, including sex. It also guarantees the right to equal job opportunities. Gender mainstreaming, introduced in 2002 through the Equal Opportunities for Women and Men Act, is a key legal tool for gender equality. The first national program on gender equality was adopted in 2005, making gender mainstreaming a cross-cutting strategy. The latest strategy, the National Programme for Equal Opportunities

2015–2020, employs both special measures and gender mainstreaming to advance practical gender equality across policies and programs.¹

Nonetheless, structural constraints in Slovenia impact gender equality across various aspects, including economic participation, leadership representation, work-life balance, education, legal frameworks, cultural norms, and healthcare access. These constraints contribute to issues like the gender wage gap, underrepresentation of women in leadership roles, and challenges in balancing work and personal life. Addressing these structural barriers is vital for advancing gender equality in Slovenia and requires a comprehensive approach involving government policies, societal shifts, and initiatives from multiple sectors.

It is important to realise that women's equality needs to be seen from several perspectives. Not only in law, but also in practice. They must have equal social power, equal representation in the spheres of public and private life and the same benefits of advancement. Equality is by no means the same thing, however, and it is therefore also necessary to look at the differences between the sexes. Slovenia has therefore drawn up a national plan for the implementation of the programme for equal opportunities for women and men, in which it has identified eight areas: equal economic independence, reconciliation of private and professional life, a knowledge society free of gender stereotypes, social inclusion, women's and men's health, balanced representation of women and men in decision-making positions, violence against women, and gender equality in foreign policy and international development cooperation.

Slovenia applies gender mainstreaming to the implementation of its strategic plans, which in practice means that for every policy, measure or criterion that is planned, we have to examine what impact and consequences it would have on women and men. The Law on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men stipulates that all ministries must appoint a coordinator or focal point to ensure that a gender perspective is integrated into measures and policies. In addition to the government and ministries, local self-governing authorities are also committed to promoting and creating equal opportunities. To facilitate these tasks, the law allows municipalities to appoint a coordinator. This shows that women have also started to make their mark in the natural sciences and technical professions and, surprisingly, the proportion of women in the IT and cyber security sectors has risen sharply. By including

women in leadership positions, Slovenia is enforcing quotas and the inclusion of the female gender in top positions.

3.6.1. Gender representation in history in Slovenia

The role of gender representation in history is an important aspect of promoting gender equality. Historically, women have been underrepresented in the field of history, both as subjects of historical research and as historians themselves. This has resulted in a lack of attention to women's experiences and contributions in historical narratives.

The available data underscores the underrepresentation of women in Slovenia, an imbalance historically influenced by significant male involvement, as well as prevailing political structures. Presently, men continue to dominate the narrative of what is commonly referred to as "visible history." Nonetheless, empirical evidence indicates that the majority of women actively contribute to the co-creation and advancement of various programs. Consequently, historical records substantiate that women played pivotal roles in formulating educational frameworks, instrumental in propelling Slovenia to its status as one of the most educationally advanced nations worldwide. Additionally, it is evident that women have traditionally spearheaded research endeavours, particularly within the medical domain, as well as fostered cultural and artistic expressions.

In response to this, Slovenia has introduced a curriculum component within primary education, dedicated to spotlighting Slovenian women who have indelibly shaped the course of history. Rozalia Sršen (1897-1967), widely regarded as Slovenia's preeminent actress, transitioned from a prominent Hollywood career to the metalworking industry, rendering her one of the most intriguing Slovenian women in historical retrospect. Likewise, Alma Maksimiljana Karlin, a distinguished researcher, author, and theosophist hailing from Celje, staunchly resisted the Nazi regime and produced over twenty literary works during her lifetime, including a highly circulated travelogue exceeding 100,000 copies in print. Owing to her exceptional literary acumen, Karlin garnered informal consideration for the Nobel Prize from Swedish circles. The curriculum further encompasses Sophie Hess, Alfred Nobel's confidante, who fabricated a compelling narrative to elicit compassion, support, and financial backing for her cause. This endeavour culminated in the establishment of a Nobel statue in

Celje. Additionally, Gizela Štrukel, an inaugural graduate of Jože Plečnik and one of Slovenia's pioneering architects, distinguished herself by crafting aesthetically captivating urban residences. Presently, Štrukel stands as a luminary in Slovenian architectural discourse and the design of commemorative monuments and sepulchers. In the realm of pharmacy, Emilija Fon stands as a trailblazer, being among the earliest women to establish her independent apothecary.

Upon retrospection, Slovenian history bears witness to a multitude of women who have etched their legacies onto the terrain of Slovenia. Figures such as Barbara Celjska, Adelma Von Vay, and Anna Schauberg, among others, have played pivotal roles in shaping Slovenia's historical narrative.

In recent years, there has been a growing awareness of the importance of including women's voices and perspectives in the study of history in Slovenia. Efforts have been made to promote research on women's history and to increase the visibility of women in historical narratives. For example, the Slovenian Women's History Network was established in 2004 to promote research on women's history and to encourage the inclusion of women in historical narratives.

There have also been efforts to increase the representation of women in the field of history itself. While women make up a majority of history students in Slovenia, they are underrepresented in academic and research positions. Efforts have been made to address this issue by promoting gender equality in academic and research institutions, including initiatives to increase the number of women in leadership positions and to address gender bias in academic hiring and promotion processes.

3.6.2. Gender representation in history in Velenje

The research and focus groups both show the importance of recognizing and highlighting the often-overlooked contributions of women in local history. In focus groups, participants shed light on various facets of gender equality and women's roles, noting challenges in researching women's history due to a lack of documentation and historical narratives. They also pointed out the glaring underrepresentation of women in street names in Velenje, a city with 102 streets named after figures from the National Liberation War period and artists, but none

after women. Efforts have been made to rectify this, with proposals for female street names being submitted. Alma Karlin, a notable polyglot, and traveller from Celje, was cited as an example of a successful promotion of a female figure in history. The conversation also touched on the significant role of mining women in Velenje's history, with participants advocating for statues or exhibits to honour their contributions. During the focus group with young people, it became evident that young people in the Šaleška dolina region have limited knowledge of local history, particularly regarding influential women. They are familiar with Alma M. Karlin's legacy, but unaware of other women who have made substantial contributions to their communities. The discussion grapples with defining exceptional individuals, highlighting that women have historically been excluded from this category due to patriarchal norms. The participants express a keen interest in understanding the roles of "miner's wives" and "female partisans," as well as the broader contributions of women in post-war reconstruction and the development of Velenje. There is an evident need to acknowledge and celebrate the multifaceted roles of women in history, while also recognizing the challenges and biases that have historically marginalized their contributions.

3.7. Lithuania

The history of Lithuanian society and statehood is quite reflective of one of the central issues concerning gender equality, namely, the challenge of turning the vision or a set of ideas into a tangible social change and bringing equality into the everyday lives of people. The first establishment of the Lithuanian Republic in 1918, period of an autocratic regime, following occupations by an ideology driven USSR, reestablishment of independence in the 1990s and a huge political transformation leading to the EU membership has made Lithuanian society face a diverse range of political visions and sets of values being promoted and often imposed on the society sometimes in a complete disregard of the social reality. Therefore, a degree of disparity between what is the officially promoted vision of the society (including the gender equality aspect) and the way how society functions in reality is perceived as natural, at least by the local population. Supporting an idea regardless of whether to survive in an oppressive regime or to join the EU does not necessarily translate into change of the social norms which are being enforced daily and remain out of control of the government officials.

This point is important given the context of official policies and legal frameworks related to gender equality and pursued by different governments over time. During the period of Soviet occupation, equality between men and women was claimed in economic and social life with specific emphasis on employment. However, this was not a matter of choice given the “full employment” policy in the USSR as well as the necessity for both partners in the family to work due to low salaries. At the same, gender stereotypes and patriarchal views remained unchallenged or reinforced as in other Central and Eastern European countries.¹⁵

Following the restoration of independence, a lot of work had to be accomplished to establish formal institutional and legal frameworks to tackle gender inequality. Namely, an Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson was established, laws on Equal Treatment and on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men passed as well as a number of international conventions ratified, and EU Directives implemented. Nevertheless, in the most recent Gender Equality index Lithuania scored 60 points out of 100 and ranked 20th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index.¹⁶ Even with the 53 % of the population being female¹⁷ Lithuania is still facing significant obstacles to gender equality mostly related to structural constraints which limit the effects of the mentioned laws and regulations.

One of the most apparent and long-existing structural constraints related to gender equality is gender segregation in the labour market. Certain sectors in Lithuania are historically dominated by male or female gender resulting in the existence of “masculine” and “feminine” sectors, choice of which prospective labour force makes even before the employment process – when starting the vocational training.¹⁸ In 2022, more than 80 % of workers were male in construction and transportation sectors, at the same time more than 80 % of workers were female in the health care and social work sector, more than 78 % – in education and more

¹⁵ Gruzevskis, B., Kanopiene, V. (2016). Lithuania. In Razzu, G. (Ed.). (2016). *Gender Inequality in the Eastern European Labour Market: Twenty-five years of transition since the fall of communism*. (1st ed., pp. 152) Taylor & Francis.

¹⁶ European Institute for Gender Equality. *Gender Equality Index*. Retrieved from: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2022/country/LT#:~:text=Best%20performance,which%20it%20scores%2073.9%20points>.

¹⁷ The World Bank Data. *Population, female (% of total population) - Lithuania*. Retrieved from: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL.FE.ZS?locations=LT>

¹⁸ Gruzevskis, B., Kanopiene, V. (2016). Lithuania. In Razzu, G. (Ed.). (2016). *Gender Inequality in the Eastern European Labour Market: Twenty-five years of transition since the fall of communism*. (1st ed., pp. 157) Taylor & Francis.

than 73 % – in accommodation and restaurant services.¹⁹ The trend remains largely unchanged since the restoration of independence. In addition to a clear horizontal gender segregation Lithuania is also facing a vertical segregation due to less women occupying leadership positions.

The segregation in the labour market also translates into wages which reinforce gender inequality even further. The gender pay gap in Lithuania in 2022 was 11.1 % and remained unchanged in comparison with 2021. The largest gender pay gaps were recorded in enterprises engaged in financial and insurance activities – 31.8 %, information and communication – 28.4 %, health care and social work activities – 25.6 %. In enterprises engaged in transportation and storage and construction activities, average gross hourly earnings of women exceeded that of men therefore the gap was negative and stood at – 11.9 % and – 3.6 % respectively.²⁰

In addition to the labour market outcomes, a major constraint in Lithuania for gender equality is insufficient reconciliation of family and work. In the 90s, there was an acute shortage of childcare facilities²¹ which limited the possibilities of mothers during that period to pursue careers and consequently still has an effect on their occupations, income and status today. Qualitative study carried out in 2020 showed that availability of pre-school childcare facilities is still one of the biggest concerns for parents.²² Other challenges indicated by the respondents include feminised discourses on childcare and lack of information for fathers, stereotypes and cultural norms, unfavourable work environment for taking parental leave, inadequate regulation of parental leave and related benefits, all of which make fathers less likely to take parental leave and putting more family responsibilities on women.²³ Analysis of the existing Lithuanian legal framework also showed asymmetry in parental rights and

¹⁹ Official Statistics Portal of Lithuania. *Average number of full- and part-time employees by economic activity*. Retrieved from: <https://osp.stat.gov.lt/en/statistiniu-rodikliu-analize?hash=d2673fd2-18e8-484f-a4e4-9ee382a079e7>

²⁰ Official Statistics Portal of Lithuania. *Gender pay gap*. Retrieved from: <https://osp.stat.gov.lt/informaciniai-pranesimai?articleId=11072310>

²¹ Gruzevskis, B., Kanopiene, V. (2016). Lithuania. In Razzu, G. (Ed.). (2016). *Gender Inequality in the Eastern European Labour Market: Twenty-five years of transition since the fall of communism*. (1st ed., pp. 163) Taylor & Francis.

²² Pilinkaitė-Sotirovič, V., Kontvainė, V. (2020). *Šiuolaikiniai vyrai ir lyčių lygybė: paskatos ir kliūtys vyrams įsitraukti į vaiko priežiūrą*. Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson. p. 31.

²³ Pilinkaitė-Sotirovič, V., Kontvainė, V. (2020). *Šiuolaikiniai vyrai ir lyčių lygybė: paskatos ir kliūtys vyrams įsitraukti į vaiko priežiūrą*. Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson. pp. 31-32.

benefits which favoured children younger than 14 years old, families with at least 2 children and mothers over fathers.²⁴

The most serious structural constraint having impact on the previously mentioned constraints too is gender stereotypes which exist in all possible spheres and affect decisions in everyday life. These stereotypes can not only affect how people treat members of other gender, but also individual decisions taken independently, such as choice of a job or education, as mentioned in the gender segregation section. Men and women in Lithuania are still mostly seen as two groups performing specific roles and functions as well as having distinct features and qualities unrelated to biological differences between sexes. According to a study carried out in 2021, when it comes to statements related to gender stereotypes, approximately one third usually supports them: statement that women should always strive to be attractive was supported by 28 %, a woman must stay at home – by 27 %, men are better drivers than women – by 23 %, men should be the main providers for the family – by 21 % of the respondents.²⁵ However, there is a positive dynamic, all of these statements were supported less than in 2019.

3.7.1. Gender representation in history in Lithuania

Lithuanian history, as in many other countries, predominantly focuses on male figures such as kings, dukes, military leaders, prominent politicians and writers. Even though there are several well-known female figures among nobility (e.g., Queen Morta, Ona Vytautienė, Bona Sforca, Emilija Pliaterytė), writers and publicists (e.g., Gabrielė Petkevičaitė-Bitė, Julija Beniuševičiūtė-Žymantienė), prominent scientists (e.g., Marija Gimbutienė), women are underrepresented and less talked about even when their importance to Lithuanian history is undisputed. Representation of women is usually based on specific and more prominent individuals and does not provide much information on the life of women in general. Analysis of the linguistic gender representation in English and Lithuanian textbooks on history

²⁴ Vanagelienė, R., Vengalė-Dits, L. (2021). *Lietuvos Respublikos teisės aktų asmeninio gyvenimo ir darbo derinimo klausimais apžvalga*. Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson.

²⁵ Lithuanian Ministry of Social Security and Labour. (2021). *Report on the sociological survey on the situation of women and men disparities between women and men in Lithuania*. pp.83. Retrieved from: [https://socmin.lrv.lt/uploads/socmin/documents/files/Projektu-konkursai/MVLG%20konkursai/Ataskaita%20-%20SADM%20Moter%C5%B3%20ir%20vyr%C5%B3%20pad%C4%97ties%20skirtumai%20LT%202021%20\(galutin%C4%97\).pdf](https://socmin.lrv.lt/uploads/socmin/documents/files/Projektu-konkursai/MVLG%20konkursai/Ataskaita%20-%20SADM%20Moter%C5%B3%20ir%20vyr%C5%B3%20pad%C4%97ties%20skirtumai%20LT%202021%20(galutin%C4%97).pdf)

confirmed that men are represented more frequently, and gender representation is imbalanced. Men are introduced as rulers, decision makers, politicians, etc. and described in similar ways: harsh, powerful, ruthless, persuasive, etc.²⁶

3.7.2. Gender representation in history in Vilnius

The History of Vilnius faces similar issues regarding gender representation, as the history of Lithuania. Even though there are famous female historical figures in the Lithuanian capital, there is a lack of publications and systemic approach focused on the role of women in the history of the city. The topic of the situation of women in Lithuanian cities used to be unexplored until recently.²⁷ It is, however, attracting more attention and there is an increasing interest in the topic both among academia and general public, specifically in the form of guided tours about the famous women of Vilnius. Some of the most recent publications about prominent women includes *Lithuanian visionaries* (Gasiulytė, E., 2020), *Women who built Lithuania* (Auškalnytė A., 2020), *Evening stories for Lithuanian girls - 100 stories about Lithuanian women* (Aprimaitė V., Uronaitė V., 2020), *Women in the twists and turns of history: rulers, artists, scientists, mystics, heroines, who shaped the history of the city and the world* (Baškienė R., 2022). In 2022, Lithuanian National Radio and Television also launched a project *Didmoterės* to commemorate women's role in Lithuanian history by publishing dedicated articles on the portal.²⁸

3.8. Italy

Gender discrimination is a social issue that stems from the cultural and structural necessity to keep the female sex in a subordinate position. We can infer that there are several patriarchal strategies employed to subjugate women in contemporary societies:

²⁶ Daržinkevič, I. (2020). *Linguistic gender representation in textbooks: a comparative study of textbooks in English and Lithuanian*. Doctoral dissertation., Vytautas Magnus University., pp.35.

²⁷ Karpavičienė, J. (2001). Moteris teisinėje Vilniaus ir Kauno kasdienoje XVI a. pirmojoje pusėje: modernėjančio gyvenimo ženklai. *Lietuvos istorijos studijos*, 9, pp. 18

²⁸ Lithuanian National Radio and Television (2022). *DIDMOTERĖS - a new project about prominent Lithuanian women on LRT.lt*. Retrieved from: <https://www.lrt.lt/naujienos/tavo-lrt/15/1749282/didmoterės-naujas-projektas-apie-iskilias-lietuvos-moteris-portale-lrt-lt>

- Economic strategies, which can be observed in the feminisation of poverty, unequal distribution of economic resources and assets, the prevalence of unpaid labour, and economic disparities between men and women.
- Symbolic strategies, which involve the general acceptance of cultural norms and values that naturalize and legitimize gender discrimination.
- Institutional strategies, manifested through the enactment of laws that encourage, allow, or fail to eradicate abuses against the female sex.
- Group violence strategies, whereby discriminatory behaviours are directed towards specific social, religious, ethnic, or economic groups.
- Interpersonal violence strategies, perpetrated by individuals against specific individuals.

Regarding the **legislative dimension**, at the **international level**, the approach is mostly to incorporate women's issues into institutions in a cross-cutting manner, although specialized institutions have emerged over time. For instance, among the general principles of the United Nations, Article 1 of the Charter already prohibits all forms of discrimination, including those based on sex. Furthermore, the organisation commits to integrating more specific rights through resolutions and conferences, such as the four World Conferences on Women. In fact, thanks to the Beijing Conference in 1995, the UN and participating states pledged to ensure the cross-cutting integration of a gender perspective in all policies and programs related to various spheres of society. It is also important to mention the creation of the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), a unit that works to eliminate inequalities and delve into the issue. Another significant milestone is the Istanbul Convention of 2011, an international treaty against violence against women and domestic violence; it aims to prevent violence and promote the protection of victims.

3.8.1. Gender representation in history in Italy

At the **national level**, in Italy, in addition to the ratification of international provisions, there are measures of comprehensive protection aimed at preventing, sanctioning, and eradicating effective inequality between men and women. First and foremost, the equality between men and women is enshrined in Articles 3, 29, 37, and 51 of the Italian Constitution, which recognizes the existence of the same rights in all areas of public and private life.

The gender equality established in the Constitution was only the first achievement in a long and arduous journey towards gender equality, which can be summarized in the following key milestones:

1950: The "Law for the Physical and Economic Protection of Working Mothers" introduces the first protections for maternity, prohibiting dismissal from the beginning of pregnancy until the child reaches one year of age.

1963: Norms are approved that prohibit dismissal in case of marriage, and Law no. 6/1963 grants full access for women to professional careers, including the judiciary.

1975: Law no. 151 on family law reform establishes equality between spouses.

1977: Approval of Law no. 903, which prohibits discrimination in access to employment, vocational training, and remuneration.

1978: Women gain the right to abortion through the adoption of Law no. 194.

1981: The Criminal Code abolishes "reparative marriage" and the crime of "honour killing" (Law no. 442).

2006: The Code of Equal Opportunities is introduced through Legislative Decree no. 198.

2019: The "Red Code" is adopted, which introduces an urgent procedure for gender-based and domestic violence crimes, tightens the sanctioning framework, defines new criminal offenses (including revenge porn), provides training for law enforcement, and rehabilitation for perpetrators of violence.

2021: Law no. 162 on gender equality in the workplace introduces certification for gender parity.

Since 2015, Italy has had the National Strategic Plan against Male Violence towards Women, aimed at promoting prevention, victim protection, punishment of offenders, training, and information.

In addition to the regulations that have come into force in recent decades, specific action plans have been developed throughout the national territory, and competencies have been

delegated to the regions to create effective measures tailored to different areas. Let's focus specifically on the steps taken in this regard by our region, Lombardia.

In 2017, the local authorities approved intervention guidelines in the fight against gender-based violence. Particularly, the Regional Council approved the *Four-Year Regional Plan for Gender Equality Policies and Prevention and Combating Violence against Women*. The plan aims to promote a culture of equality and recognition of fundamental human rights in economic, social, and family spheres. The regional action seeks to strengthen all anti-violence centres and specialized facilities in the area and ensure effective prevention policies.

Gender representation is a fundamental concept in crucial fields like history, as it contributes to ensuring a more inclusive and comprehensive perspective of human experiences. Since its inception, history has often given greater prominence to the narratives and achievements of men, neglecting or undervaluing the voices and contributions of women and other gender minorities. This has led to a distorted view of the past and a lack of awareness of the various facets of historical experiences.

Gender representation in history is important to include diverse perspectives, remove limiting gender stereotypes, make visible new role models that have been silenced so far, have a more accurate and multifaceted historical framework, and promote gender equality throughout different historical periods.

To incorporate greater gender representation in history, it is essential to involve historians, educators, museum curators, and other key figures in the process of historical research and storytelling. Initiatives aimed at recovering, preserving, and disseminating the stories of women and gender minorities should be supported, both through inclusion in school curricula and through exhibitions, publications, and other forms of historical dissemination. Only through a consistent commitment to broaden our understanding of history can we build a more inclusive and just society.

4. Key Findings by the organised Focus Groups with stakeholders transnationally

4.1. Salamanca, Spain

Two focus groups with stakeholders were organised, involving 11 participants with different profiles.

4.1.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

Some Stakeholders mention that the link with history has been little, and that perhaps very little is dedicated to seeing what is current and focuses a lot on the old, so it is difficult to rescue what has not been made known or made visible at the time, however, it has been in their work where they have become aware of the importance of making women visible, such as women in STEM, or the visibility of women researchers in history, technologists, also working with other communities such as people with disabilities or LGTB+ people. We know a little about history and what was given to them and what they were interested in for their own interest or particular character at some point, but very little about the history of women. Moreover, history has always been told from the male perspective. The invisibility of women is almost complete. There is a very long history of women. The main and most active participation is on 11 February (International Day of Women and Girls in Science) through different associations across Europe, such as the Association of Women in Research and Technology in Spain (AMIT) and other members of the European Platform of Women Scientists, where women in research are made visible.

4.1.2. Findings on 'History through the lens of their expertise'

Some stakeholders consider that their lack of time or inexperience limits them in the transmission of content, leaving aside topics such as gender perspective or history. They often focus on current affairs, because young people are losing interest, and they see current content or more contemporary characters as more relatable and identifiable. Another big challenge is the content of textbooks, which contain very few female figures. Another

challenge is the bias in the interpretation and language used, as well as the loss of identity. It must be institutionalised and not just a matter of voluntarism. It must be integrated into the curriculum and taught as a matter of course.

4.1.3. Findings on 'Experience with young people in the field of History'

It is complicated to see the interest of children and young people. It is not that they are not interested in the history of women in Salamanca (Spain), it is just the way it is presented to them, the same happens with other subjects such as mathematics, language. There is little interest, but not much less than in other subjects. Incorporating gender issues in the classroom is important, even if it is met with a certain amount of boredom on the part of the young people, resistance that is difficult to overcome. The lack of interest on the part of young people is related to the fact that the education system does not provide them with information related to women. The role of making teachers visible is important, having the interest to provide this content. There are young people who already have some previous interest, who are proactive and when they are given more information, their interest is awakened.

4.1.4. Findings on 'Women's footprint in History'

Methods of transmission

- Practical, tangible things so that it is internalised, manageable and interactive. It is very important how it is told.
- In libraries, narratives can be created from images, references in works of literature.
- Implement active methodologies.
- Gamification.
- Project work.
- Inverted classes.
- Launch a competition in schools. Let them make videos, comics, audios .
- Introduce the intersectional perspective.
- The importance of women in all public spaces must be communicated and publicised at an early stage.

Representation

Male characters are well represented, the focus should be on women only. It is always necessary to disseminate for men and women and not to segregate men and boys. The diversity of scientific and historical knowledge should be presented. Represent women careers, women who have done social work in the history of Salamanca. Recover the memory of women in the different disciplines. When it comes to recovering the memory, the intersectional perspective must be introduced, as the memory of university women, literate women, high and low social classes, etc. must be recovered.

Transnational Map

- An interactive map.
- Introduce gamification, perhaps make it like a geocaching map.
- Use more graphic things, such as introducing the information of the woman in a monument and by passing the mobile phone over it, it gives you all the information.
- A map with simple information, simple, short, like an infographic, very visual and complement it with small videos.
- Focus not only on historical places but also outside the city.

Collaborations

- Connect with public libraries, implement activities in them.
- Connect with associations that offer activities, complementary workshops such as the Ciudad de los Niños programme and youth centres.
- Collaboration with influencers, public figures, ambassadors who talk about women's legacies in history.
- Sightseeing tours.
- It is important not only to recover the memory of women, but also spaces and meeting places.

Digital Tools

- TikTok.
- Memes.

- Using artificial intelligence to tell a message, give women a voice and let them tell their story.
- Video games.
- Social networks: Instagram, Facebook.
- Mobile App.

4.1.5. Suggestions from participants on female footprint in the city/in history

- Teresa Vicente Mosquete. Dept. Geography. She wrote a book: Streets with a woman's name: Women in the streets. A history to be written on the walls of our cities - *Calles con nombre de mujer: La mujer en el callejero. Una historia por escribir en los muros de nuestras ciudades*, in *La historia no contada: Mujeres pioneras 2007*.
- María Telo Nuñez was the protagonist of the reforms of the Civil Code in 1975 and 1981, the third woman to be awarded Honoris Causa in the history of the University of Salamanca.
- Lucía de Medrano, María Maeztu linked to the University of Salamanca.
- Magdalena Garretas, who was Unamuno's assistant.
- Ana Díaz Medina. She was the first director of the Seminary, a specialist in modern history. She was the first to implement a subject on the history of modern women in the Faculty of History, and from then on, the following courses were developed.

4.2. Martinique, France

One Focus Group with stakeholders was organised, involving 4 participants with different profiles.

Most of the stakeholders interested in the project and who could participate in the focus group are people who have studied or work in the field of history and/or gender. This explains why they have experience or a rather solid knowledge in the field of history. Some people who are not from this field were interested but were unable to take part in the focus group (for example, people from the prefecture or other associations).

Their expertise showed that women are poorly represented in history and their participation in shaping our societies is not documented. Madame Celma, for example, who works for the

Union des femmes Martinique (UFM)⁹ began in the 1980s working on social movements. She realized that there were always women present, that some of them had played an important role, but that it was never highlighted. Today, work is being done to make these women better known, but they face challenges in terms of content, in particular the lack of information and documentation. Therefore, working on the footprint of women in history requires an enormous amount of time. Whether it be in archives or elsewhere, there is very little information available compared to what can be found on men. Their experiences, struggles, and agency were often absent from official historical archives, which shows the little importance attributed to women in history.

Their experience with young people showed that most of them don't have enough information and knowledge in the history field. Content-wise, there is a lack and what young people need the most, is an intersectional perspective. History always addresses the white male point of view, and deliberately omits the "others' stories". Depending on their intersections (gender, origins, sexual orientation, class, etc.), people are more or less likely to be represented in the telling of the History.

However, they believe that some young people are interested in history so it would be possible to interest most of them and make them more aware of history. Concerning the interest in women's history, they feel that it is growing, especially among young women, as they are seeking for identification and searching for heroines who resemble them. But to succeed in interesting as many people as possible, we need to succeed in generating that interest. For this purpose, there are several tools that could be used. It would be interesting, for example, to use storytelling or to ask them to represent one figure, by role-playing, miming, or drawing inspiration from what Adeline Rapon¹⁰ has done. It's important for young people to be actors themselves. It would also be interesting to use short documentaries, games, theatre plays or gymkhana with QR codes, apps or board games where you can trace a "feminist timeline".

What the stakeholders see is that the contribution of women in history is rarely highlighted which also explains why young people and others have little knowledge or interest in the subject. In general, women in Martinique are forgotten on the national scale, but locally there are also concerns. However, many women in Martinique have contributed to history but their

footprint in history is weak. Even if the participants can refer to the female footprint in history, most of them had to learn about the role of women in history outside their formal studies. They learned about it late and either by their entourage or through personal research. This shows the lack of women's footprint in history.

Good practices to promote gender balance in history would be to introduce women's participation every time we talk about history. It's important to highlight women and men's role and it's crucial to make every person aware of why it is important to promote gender balance in history.

Non-Formal education activities (games, leisure activities, sports, etc) could also be a good way to promote gender equality.

4.3. Nicosia, Cyprus

Two focus groups with stakeholders were organised, involving 11 participants.

4.3.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

All the stakeholders that participated in the Focus Group were representing Institutions, Research Centres and Civil Society's organisations in the field of History, Gender, Human Rights, and some of them were also part of Local Authorities.

Three of them were members of Research Centres and Organisations that implements research in Gender History and in Human Rights. Four of them were members of Human Rights Organisations and groups of Civil Society. One of them is currently working in a university and specifically in the Department of Diversity and one of the participants was the first ever female Mayor of Nicosia, Cyprus' capital.

All the institutions that were represented in the Focus Group are working to promote gender perspective, each in their own field of interest. Their actions are addressing gender equality by raising equal gender visibility through multisector initiatives. Some of the fields that they are working on are gender & sports, gender & culture, gender & working rights, gender & history and gender & media. In each area of interest, the participants are working hard by

developing activities, projects and local actions through the lens of gender perspective and by promoting female visibility in order to combat gender misrepresentation.

4.3.2. Findings on 'History through the lens of their expertise'

Participants agreed that history is a gender biased topic which is written by the already male-dominant civil groups of societies. All participants also agreed on the difficulties that they are facing when they are trying to implement the gender perspective aspect in their research field. Furthermore, they added that finding information related to the female's footprint in history is really challenging.

Thus, some of their findings are gender biased. Some of the participants added that these challenges come from the lack of state mechanisms on recording women's contribution in history and they pointed out the lack of funding on such initiatives as a crucial milestone on these procedures.

The participants also mentioned that gender stereotypes are strictly rooted in Cypriot society and thus, there is this narrative that women were only placed in the private sector and that's the reason why institutions and researchers find it hard to retrieve information and data. However, they acknowledged the fact this is not something that is only a myth because based on their findings and their expertise in the field they often find evidence of women's examples who managed to gain their own space in their field of interest without anyone giving them any opportunities. Additionally, gender norms of what is considered as a "great achievement" reflects on what is being archived and what is not.

The participants agreed that even though they have expertise in this specific field of research, they believe that there is still a lot of lack of knowledge regarding women who contributed either collectively or anonymously.

4.3.3. Findings on 'Experience with young people in the field of History'

Participants of the Focus Group mentioned the crucial role of the education system when it comes to knowledge, information and opportunities. Young people seem to be interested in learning more about gender and female's footprint in history, however they don't have the

right tools to gain such knowledge neither are they given the space they need nor the encouragement or the support.

Some of the participants mentioned some challenges that they have noticed throughout their experience when working with young people. They pointed out that, nowadays, young people are born, raised and influenced by the male-dominant narrative and that is really challenging when it comes to topics such as gender equality. Young people believe that all people have equal rights and equal opportunities and thus, they don't feel the need to act towards gender equality.

However, stakeholders mentioned that their experience with this group of people, shows that young people who have developed social voluntary action, are more sensible to such issues. While all stakeholders agreed that they detect interest in young people's opinions in gender perspective topics, however, despite that, they still find difficulties on how to influence and affect them more.

4.3.4. Findings on 'Women's footprint in history'

Stakeholders that have participated in the Focus Group have mentioned the following women's footprint examples in history:

- The building where the first women telephone operators were working (CYTA Building, Nicosia, Cyprus)
- Electra Building (close to the Ledra Palas)
- Female school '*Parthenagogio*'
- The Royal Hall (venue of the first women's organisation conference)
- Vasilissis Olgas Street ('*Vasilissis*' comes from the Greek word '*vasilissa*' which means "Queen")
- Vasilissis Friderikis Street
- Melina Merkouri Street
- Evgenia Theodotou Street

4.3.5. Suggestions on tools to promote women's footprint in history

General Suggestions

- Non-formal education tools.
- Participatory education to increase interest.
- Experiential learning.

Digital Tools

- Audio-visual material
- Statues & monuments with scan signs where the visitor could scan and listen to the background story.
- Story telling & use the Cypriot dialect in order to attract the young people more.
- The developed map could be combined with videos.

Collaborations

- Nicosia Municipality
- All of the organisations & institutions that were participating in the Focus Group stated their desire to contribute in any way to the projects' activities.

4.4. Athens, Greece

One focus group with stakeholders was organised, involving 12 participants with different profiles.

4.4.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

Most of the participants had a high level of relevance with the field of History, as they were educators and academics. One participant was specialized in history and has deployed dedicated research to women of modern history. Two educators from the group had experience in projects with young people, focusing on gender equality through history.

"I recently finished my post-doctoral research, which was about the history of women, both living and non-living, from the interwar period to the present day, especially women who have survived torture. I focused mainly on the seven-year period, because that's where the bulk of

the living women are, some are very well known, some not at all known, but that doesn't matter".

4.4.2. Findings on 'History through the lens of their expertise'

All participants shared that history is important as a topic, however the way it is taught from elementary school up to university, makes it very difficult to engage young people. They have highlighted the lack of new media and contemporary ways of teaching, and this creates a gap with how young people receive information and knowledge today. Moreover, regarding the content, some participants noted that we miss elements from modern history after World War two, and more specifically historical moments after the 1950s.

Furthermore, a very important finding was the acknowledgement from the participants that history was written in a way that didn't include gender and for that reason also Greek language is focused on using male gender in written or oral discourse.

"The problems of gender in history begin with vocabulary. The discourse we use and the discourse in which our historical texts are written, in any case, does not have a gender dimension".

4.4.3. Findings on 'Experience with young people in the field of History'

Some of the educators of the group had experience in working with young people in shelters of unaccompanied children. Although they didn't report their experience with teaching history, they mentioned their experience in interacting with young people about historical events and gender equality. They pointed out how important it is for young people to learn about gender equality and how much they are interested in this topic, but also how difficult it is for them to understand the elements of gender equality and how to implement it in everyday life.

Participants highlighted the fact that young people have little knowledge about history in general and this becomes worse in historical achievements by female figures. Moreover, they mentioned the importance of technology in promoting history to young people, and specifically the use of social media and other interactive media.

"About history we refer to when we do an action or on the occasion of International Women's Day; various such actions, talking about equality, we also refer to female figures.

"If you talk about equality and discrimination, they will say we agree that we are all equal, women have the same rights as us. But in reality, in their everyday life you will see that this is not true."

"It is true that the young people do not seem to have good knowledge, neither qualitatively nor quantitatively, but the children are very interested and that is very important. I mean you see that when you tell them something, their interest in history is immediately revived".

"The beneficiaries show that they are ignorant, they don't know women figures of importance".

"I think now young people are attracted to social media and image. I think it's the image that they're more engaged with. So, I think that some videos that talk about such people but in an interesting way, maybe it would pique their curiosity and interest a little bit."

4.4.4. Findings on 'Women's footprint in History'

There is a great difficulty in the research of elements regarding women's footprint in history and specific information regarding female figures. However, some very important information was revealed during this focus group. One great example is the importance of the guerilla for the position of women during the Second World War. Guerilla and the war placed women in a different situation, outside of home, having an important role in espionage and in supporting their home in a different way when men were away.

Moreover, it was mentioned that even if in some areas there is a reference to a female figure, it is very difficult to find more information about this person and its achievements. Most of the time it is only a superficial reference and women are mentioned only as a name. The lack of extended knowledge regarding women that have gained high reputation, was commonly agreed.

"With a search I did to look for historical female figures, I found that there is very little reference to very little, at least in Larissa where I am, I found almost nothing in reference to a historical female figure who has left an era and is remembered".

"The women themselves reported that the guerrilla, for example, took them out of the house and gave them a place to stay. This is very, very important, that is, from where they did not exist, which were purely productive units in the home or in the fields, they gained a place in society, they took up positions that men could not carry out".

4.4.5. Suggestions from participants on female footprint in the city/in history

Several female Greek figures in history in various fields were identified in this group, from various areas across Greece and mostly from the city of Athens. These are presented below:

- Diotima, Sappho (from ancient times)
- Aggeliki Panagiotatou (the first Greek female doctor, from the island of Kefallonia)
- Manto Mavrogenous, Bouboulina (from Greek War of Independence)
- Kalliroi Parren (the woman who started the feminist movement in Greece)
- Eleni Skoura (the first female member of the Parliament)
- Lina Tsaldari (the first female minister)
- Kaiti Tsarouxa, Xristina Moustakli (from Civil war and they are still alive)
- Lela Karagianni
- Kitti Arseni
- Melina Mercouri

One recommendation was to place a special focus in the recent years and especially the period after 1974, when trying to highlight the important female figures. This is a more recent history and can be more engaging to young people. Moreover, some women are still alive, and this might attract the interest of young people to learn more about these women and their achievement.

"So, the recent for us and the part that is incomplete in both books and teaching, is that we have all got up to 1974. We should be looking for women from 1974 to 2023".

4.5. Sofia, Bulgaria

One focus group with stakeholders was organised, involving 16 participants with different profiles.

4.5.1. Findings on ‘History through the lens of their expertise’

The stakeholders involved in the focus group listed the following main challenges they face when creating and presenting content about women's contributions or when discussing the topic of equality between men and women with youngsters:

- Stereotypical views of history as a male-dominated field.
- General stereotypical perceptions of women as equally capable to men in different spheres.
- Insufficient history recorded about women – as mentioned by the stakeholders, recorded history is usually the “history of power”, and since women were rarely in power through most of history, their contributions are not recorded or, if recorded, are sometimes attributed to men (the “Matilda” effect).
- Inadequate and outdated methodological resources for teachers – books that predominantly focus on male history, leaving out the movements for women rights and accomplishments by women.
- Limited commemoration of historic women figures in public places, such as through monuments or commemorative plaques – there are barely any, devoted to women in Bulgaria.

Moreover, the stakeholders discussed the difficulties in engaging a diverse audience to content, related to women's historical influence or their specific accomplishments in science, arts, etc. Such events are predominantly visited by passionate activists for gender equality but rarely attract the general public. Celebrations such as the ones for International Women's Day are among the few exceptions that lead to increased engagement with a more diverse audience.

4.5.2. Findings on ‘Experience with young people in the field of History’

The participants shared that the youngsters in Bulgaria are curious and interested in different modern topics, including gender equality and history. Those with sparked up interest may be few, but they follow the topics vividly and passionately. When it comes to equality or women representation, the numbers of interested young people increase every year, including the share of girls in entrepreneurship initiatives. More and more young women are stepping up and gaining confidence to work or study in their desired field, despite the bias and stereotypes.

All stakeholders agree that gender issues should be implemented and discussed as part of the formal curriculum to combat different stereotypes arising in society. Currently, it’s not being actively taught in school, the topic is brought up only in case the teacher is passionate about it. If fair gender representation is to be discussed with young people both in formal and informal education, it would require proper tools to make the topic more accessible to youngsters, such as:

- Games
- Quizzes
- Role plays
- Missions
- Experiential learning
- Videos, etc.

4.5.3. Findings on ‘Women’s footprint in History’

Representation

The stakeholders agreed that emphasis should be put on the remembrance of women across various disciplines. When seeking to recover their memory and underline their history and achievements, it is crucial to adopt an intersectional perspective, encompassing the experiences of women from different backgrounds and different occupations, such as university-educated women, literate women, freedom fighters, etc.

Transnational HerStory map

The map should be interactive and include challenges (missions) that upon completion by the visitors award them with points or some small tokens/physical stamps to collect. The app should have a long and short version, one for the very passionate tour-goers and another for the simply curious people – with and without the challenges. The participants also recommended a paper version of the map for offline tours. The map can be easily made accessible through QR-codes. Live meetings with successful women here and now may be organised in parallel to promote the map even further and to link it to nowadays, providing context and a modern touch. Animation works well with youngsters too. A set of videos (filmed/animated) can be released in TikTok for each of the women to highlight their stories. Additionally, some detective games/mysteries can be created with the collected stories of women to engage youngsters.

4.6. Valenje, Slovenia

Two focus groups were organised, involving 8 participants with different profiles.

4.6.1. Findings on ‘Relevance with the field of History’

The participants in the project represented a diverse array of roles closely tied to the field of history and cultural heritage. These roles encompassed individuals actively engaged in various aspects of historical preservation, education, research, and museum management. Among the participants were employees of Villa Mayer, specialists focused on preserving and popularizing cultural heritage. Others had experience in teaching at the Technical School and Gymnasium, contributing directly to historical education. Additionally, there were historians and curators at Velenje Museum, responsible for documentation, museum collections management, and historical research. Furthermore, a librarian from the Velenje Library brought expertise in history and sociology of culture to the discussion, while a representative from the Velenje Tourist Board, a significant entity in tourism, represented the tourist sector. This diverse and multifaceted assembly of roles collectively enhances the project's exploration of history and its multifaceted significance.

4.6.2. Findings on 'History through the lens of their expertise'

Participants in this conversation, experts in gender equality and women's historical roles, focused on the challenges of researching and documenting women's history, along with historical perceptions of feminism and women's unique expressions of power. They highlighted the difficulty in finding information about women's contributions due to their often private and less-documented roles compared to men in more public positions. Additionally, participants discussed specific historical periods, such as miners' widows facing significant challenges. They noted the context of feminism being viewed unfavourably under socialism and the impact of positive discrimination, particularly in the Soviet Union. The participants also recognized women's adaptability and excellence across various fields, often referred to as "multipractitioners." They highlighted a strong female presence in the tourism sector, where women hold significant leadership roles and drive progress. Overall, the discussion illuminated the evolving narrative of women's historical roles and the persistent challenges in uncovering their contributions.

4.6.3. Findings on 'Experience with young people in the field of History'

The participants in this discussion are experienced in working with young people in the field of history, acting as mentors and guides, offering valuable advice and support to budding historians. They have been actively involved in educational outreach at academic institutions, demonstrating a commitment to sharing historical expertise with students, particularly in the domain of gender and women's history. The feedback on young people's engagement with history is mixed. While there's recognition of the prevalence of digital distractions, there's also an acknowledgment of opportunities to educate them about historical and gender-related topics through innovative approaches. The participants note that young people are attuned to modern trends, especially in terms of gender definitions influenced by social networks. They emphasize efforts to make history more engaging for the youth, mentioning initiatives like the Young Museum and educational programs. However, there's concern about a potential gap in presenting everyday life and local history in schools, making it less relatable to students.

Stakeholders propose creating resources like maps highlighting exceptional women in history to make the subject more appealing. The main reasons cited for the lack of interest in history among young people include:

- digital distractions,
- a perception of history as less engaging,
- gender disparities in curriculum representation, and
- a need for innovative educational tools.

The participants suggest various interactive and immersive learning methods, such as role-playing, multimedia presentations, and collaborative learning, to make history a dynamic and engaging subject for the youth. They also emphasize the importance of presenting history as a living, evolving narrative rather than static facts.

4.6.4. Findings on 'Women's footprint in History'

In this discussion, the participants shed light on several facets of gender equality and women's roles in history. They mention the challenges faced in researching women's history, emphasizing the lack of documentation and historical narratives regarding women, especially those in the private sphere. They discuss the historical roles of women in various contexts, including their contributions to society, politics, and the workplace.

The participants highlighted the underrepresentation of women in Velenje's street names.

Velenje has 102 streets named after people from the NOB (National Liberation War) period and artists, but none are named after women. Participants discussed the absence of female names on streets and suggested that efforts have been made to change this, with proposals for female street names being submitted.

Additionally, they mentioned Alma Karlin, a notable woman from Celje, as an example of a successful promotion of a female figure in history. Alma Karlin was a polyglot and traveller, and her contributions to history have gained recognition. The conversation also touched on the role of mining women in Velenje's history and their significant contributions.

Participants expressed the need to acknowledge and celebrate the roles of women in history, including miners' wives, and proposed the idea of dedicating statues or exhibits to women's

contributions in the mining industry. Finally, the text mentioned ongoing collaborations and projects related to women's history, particularly focusing on the centenary of a woman's birth.

4.7. Vilnius, Lithuania

One focus group was organised, involving 5 participants with different profiles. Three individual interviews took place with experts in history and with tour guides of Vilnius city.

In both the focus group discussions and individual interviews, participants highlighted the numerous challenges associated with creating content that focuses on women's contributions to history. These challenges can be broadly categorized as follows:

- a) Lack of historiography: Participants noted the scarcity of historical research and documentation specifically dedicated to women's experiences and achievements. This shortage of source material presents a significant obstacle to accurately portraying women's roles in history.
- b) Lack of methodological material for teachers: Educators often lack sufficient resources and guidance to effectively incorporate women's history into their teaching methods. Without appropriate methodologies and teaching materials, it becomes challenging for teachers to integrate this content into their curricula in a meaningful way.
- c) Stereotypical view of history as a male-dominated subject: There exists a pervasive stereotype that history primarily focuses on the deeds and accomplishments of men, contributing to the marginalization of women's contributions. This narrow perspective of history perpetuates gender biases and inhibits the recognition of women's historical significance.
- d) Difficulties in attracting a diverse audience: Content related to women's history is often perceived as relevant only to women, leading to challenges in engaging a broader and more diverse audience. Moreover, there is a particular struggle in capturing the interest of young men, who may not see themselves reflected in narratives centered on women's experiences.

e) Lack of commemoration of women in public spaces: Participants noted the absence of public recognition and commemoration of women who have made significant contributions to history. The lack of statues, monuments, and other forms of public acknowledgment perpetuates the erasure of women's achievements from collective memory and public discourse.

These challenges show that society needs to work together to fill in the gaps in how history represents women. It should be made sure that women's contributions are more visible. If these problems are overcome, it would be possible to have a history that includes everyone's experiences and achievements, no matter their gender.

Research participants also indicated that due to stereotypical attitudes and still existing resistance to the questions related to the feminist tradition it is a challenge to draw attention to such topic as women's footprint in history. As one of the experts shared that people working in this field still have to prove why this topic is important to be taken into account and to find ways to make the topic visible and heard.

One significant reason for the lack of women's representation in the field of history is the prevailing narrative of masculinity, which became particularly entrenched during the Soviet era. During this period, historical content primarily focused on two main themes: the working class, often portrayed in a gender-neutral manner, and male figures depicted as heroes and warriors. Consequently, women's stories and contributions were largely overlooked, resulting in their virtual disappearance from Lithuanian history for a considerable period.

The emphasis on male-centric narratives reinforced traditional gender roles and obscured the roles and achievements of women throughout history. This longstanding focus on masculine ideals perpetuated the marginalization of women's voices and obscured their significant contributions to various aspects of society. As a result, the historical record presented a skewed perspective that failed to accurately reflect the diverse experiences and contributions of women in shaping Lithuanian history.

The research participants noted that more visible changes related to women representation were noticed about five years ago, when first books about women who left their footprint in Lithuania's history were published and the first guiding tours about important female

personalities who used to live in Vilnius city were organised. Furthermore, recently the number of the exhibitions devoted for women who left footprint in history increased in Vilnius city. For instance, exhibitions for famous Lithuanian archaeologist and anthropologist Marija Gimbutiene (Gimbutas) and Lithuanian-born artist Aleksandra Kasuba, special exhibition on “Women warriors” telling the stories of women warriors of the 19th and 20th centuries, and others. However, the research participants shared that they still miss representation of women as independent and heroic figures. The representation of women as a ‘passive’ figure (as someone’s wife, daughter, mother, etc.) is still more widespread. Furthermore, the experts emphasised despite the visible changes on women representation, the education system on this subject has been changing at its slowest pace.

Research participants agreed that the teaching methods currently employed in schools to deliver history lessons are outdated and fail to resonate with the younger generation. Despite the natural curiosity and eagerness of today's youth to learn, it is crucial to adopt approaches that effectively engage them. Experts offered valuable insights into potential methods that could capture the interest of young people, not only in the topic of women's contributions to history but also in the subject of history in general:

a) Implement interactive and innovative methods: using various games and digital technologies can make history lessons more engaging and interactive for students. By incorporating interactive elements into the curriculum, educators can create a dynamic learning environment that appeals to the digital-savvy younger generation.

b) Talk about the historical facts through the eyes of young person: By framing historical events and narratives through the eyes of young individuals and providing examples that resonate with their experiences, educators can make history more relatable and emotionally impactful for students. This approach helps students connect with the subject matter on a personal level, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation for history.

c) Organizing activities outside of the school: Offering activities outside the traditional classroom setting, such as watching targeted movies and performances, visiting installations and exhibitions, or participating in guided tours, can provide students with hands-on experiences that bring history to life. These immersive activities not only supplement

classroom learning but also offer students opportunities to explore history in a more interactive and engaging manner.

By implementing these innovative approaches, educators can make history lessons more relevant, interactive, and appealing to today's youth, thereby fostering a deeper interest and appreciation for both the topic of women's contributions to history and the study of history in general.

The research participants emphasised that while creating the content on female footprint in history, it should be considered women representation equal to men representation also emphasising their cooperation and common participation in certain historical events. The aim should be to show a comprehensive picture of the chosen historic event or certain time of history. Furthermore, the content of women footprint in history should be interesting both for girls and boys. It should be emphasized that there is a history of humankind and both women and men put a contribution to it and developed it cooperating. It would be a great success if boys also found emotional relation to the told stories on women's footprint in history.

4.8. Lecco, Italy

One focus group was organised, involving 8 participants with different profiles.

4.8.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

In comparison to the historical dimension, stakeholders report the absence of historical female figures within the territory of Valle San Martino, the place under investigation. The only female figure closely linked to the territory of Lecco is that of Lucia Mondella, but she is a fictional character. Lucia is, in fact, the protagonist of the historical novel "The Betrothed" by Alessandro Manzoni, set precisely in the area of Lecco. Our women also observe how history, typically learned in schools, is based almost exclusively on the deeds of men, following an androcentric perspective. It is important, instead, to adopt a more inclusive viewpoint, even concerning traditional history.

The stakeholders emphasize the importance of focusing on the everyday stories of ordinary women, searching for what they define as the "silenced history." It is crucial to be able to see

these women and their stories, giving them space, even just within the small contexts in which they lived or operated. For our women, the key lies in storytelling: to make known and spread these stories through different means and to diverse audiences.

According to our stakeholders, the history of a territory must now, more than ever, take into account a globalized world, where cultures meet, sometimes merging, while other times maintaining distinct and contrasting traits (some of them bring up the example of schools, where there are parents from non-Western cultures where the patriarchal dimension is still strong, requiring special attention).

Our women advocate the need for reflection on motherhood, understood as a life phase experienced by many, with its myriad facets. Becoming a mother, giving birth to a child, creates new balances and subtle connections; for some, it offers opportunities for self-discovery and a leap into new personal and professional experiences (as seen with our woman Romina); for others, it represents a "necessary" stage to be a woman, to understand a woman/mother; for yet others, it becomes an obstacle to their professional career, where they may need to "scale down the hierarchy" after having a child; and for someone else, it becomes a social pressure, an almost obligatory stage in the eyes of others, limiting their drive, creating feelings of inadequacy and lack.

Regarding this topic, it is also essential to provide equal space and knowledge of the rights and responsibilities of both mothers and fathers, promoting awareness of the law and breaking old stereotypes.

4.8.2. Findings on 'History through the lens of their expertise'

The sharing of their personal, professional, and lived experiences, along with acquired skills and viewpoints, by the stakeholders has led to reflections that intertwine the past and the present.

Each of them highlights how the place and historical period in which one is born and raised leave a strong imprint on each individual; it is a contextual dimension that profoundly influences a person's development. Family and family history, more or less anchored to traditional educational and cultural patterns, have influenced their academic, work, and personal growth paths.

The specific territorial dimension in which they were born and raised, the Valle San Martino and more generally the province of Lecco, represent small, still "closed" territories that have engendered a reciprocal exchange: while the territory provides support, closeness, and a sense of belonging, creating a strong bond, in each woman, there arises a desire to actively contribute to its care and enhancement.

According to our women, history is constructed through concrete models capable of influencing, sometimes even unconsciously, someone's choices. Our teacher Alessandra gives the example of the school where she teaches, where out of 40 teachers, there is only one man. This absence of male figures does not offer male children the opportunity to recognize themselves in their own gender and in the opposite one. Consequently, even among professionals, an opportunity for exchanging ideas and different perspectives is lost.

In their experiences of growth, our women recognize the importance of travel as an opportunity for meeting, comparison, and openness to others and differences. While travel provides a chance to learn about new models, cultures, and stories, the constant exchange diminishes the individuality of each of them and creates a sense of homogeneity (this dimension is even more pronounced today due to globalisation and mass media).

4.8.3. Findings on 'Experience with young people in the field of History'

Over the years, controversial thoughts have arisen regarding the construction of gender, but undoubtedly, it stems from a social division that changes over time and space, conditioning people's thoughts and actions. Gender is situated within a complex sex/gender system: the sex category, which in animal species refers to purely physical and innate characteristics related to reproduction, in the human species delves into a socio-cultural structure that is determinant. Currently, there exist different roles that classify customs and practices into expressions of femininity and masculinity. At birth, each individual is assigned a gender identity that will be expanded throughout life, actively and passively, through messages and behaviours.

According to our stakeholders, it is important to take active action to change the sex/gender dichotomy that has developed throughout history in all societies worldwide and positions women in a particular condition in the social hierarchy. To achieve this, the most effective

method for them is engaging with the younger generations: having conversations with boys and girls, creating opportunities for exchange, and together modelling new practices and references.

Our teacher Alessandra presents the experience of the association of which she is the president, "L'Isola della Stupidera" (The Island of Nonsense): this space not only offers help to children in their extracurricular educational activities but also constitutes a shared and educational experience. Every day, high school boys are involved as educators, a profession typically associated with female figures; the aim is, on one hand, to let boys also experience a role of care and education, and on the other hand, to offer children male figures who embody that role. The keywords of "L'Isola della Stupidera" are, therefore: looking, valuing, seeing, opening, and broadening horizons.

Fulvia, a member of Soroptimis, a free association of women engaged in professional and managerial activities in various fields of society, shares the initiative "SifaSTEM." It is a university orientation project for female students interested in STEM subjects (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). The goal is to motivate girls to pursue their dreams, free from prejudices, and to courageously dare to pursue scientific training paths. The world of work greatly needs technical knowledge. Fulvia emphasizes the need to break down gender biases concerning STEM subjects, increase the number of girls in STEM fields, and help them make informed choices not dictated by society's concepts and stereotypes.

4.8.4. Findings on 'Women's footprint in History'

The stakeholders highlight the absence, within the territory under investigation, of "traces" of women in different historical epochs. According to them, this absence can be traced back to a historical-cultural dimension that has always been based on the valorisation of typically male and heroic models, while giving little recognition to the everyday, simple but fundamental actions of ordinary women.

One cause of this absence can be found in the limited female participation in social life. Throughout history, the social construction of gender has kept public and private spaces separate, assigning the former to men and the latter to women. Thus, women have always been recognized for their caregiving roles in the private sphere, but these actions have

remained invisible to society. During the particular period of industrialisation, this dichotomy became even more accentuated, with notions of "political, power, community, public" attributed solely to men.

In the last few decades, the feminist movements of the 1960s and 1970s have advocated for the need to analyse women's conditions in the past, breaking away from the traditional framework of an androcentric historical discipline. To overcome these limitations, feminism has introduced new methods, concepts, and categories capable of giving voice to women and social groups that were previously silenced.

Our women view history as a continuum between the past, present, and future. From this perspective, the footprints of women today become a fundamental tool for change in the future. It is essential to value the meaningful experiences of women today, moving beyond the gender dimension and focusing instead on individuality and uniqueness. To generate such a change, a key role must be given to families and educational contexts that accompany the growth of children from a very young age.

4.8.5. Suggestions from participants on female footprint in the city/in history.

The stakeholders emphasize the importance of giving voice: narrating, telling stories, and actively involving the new generations. This allows for creating cross-cutting communication that reaches individuals of all ages and communities, both men and women. In this way, it is possible to value the footprints in local territories and throughout different moments in history.

Furthermore, according to our women, it is crucial to free every individual from old traditional gender stereotypes. This means that this issue should not remain solely the concern of women. It is essential to recognize that men also have the power to bring about change in this regard. Not all men are necessarily the sole providers of the family's economic well-being, or the ones who are physically and emotionally strong. They are complex and unique individuals who go beyond these stereotypes, just as women do. To break free from the societal weight of gender differences, it is vital to highlight the individuality of each one of us and leave new footprints capable of creating new stories.

By breaking down gender stereotypes and recognizing the unique qualities and abilities of every individual, we can foster a more inclusive and equal society where both men and women have the opportunity to thrive and contribute positively to their communities. This approach leads to a more profound understanding of each other's experiences, challenges, and aspirations, ultimately working towards a more equitable and harmonious world.

5. Key Findings by the organised Focus Groups with young people transnationally

5.1. Salamanca, Spain

Two focus groups were organised involving 6 participants.

5.1.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

There has been very little training in history, it has been the interviewees' own interest that has led them to investigate more about history and find certain information that interested them, this helped to generate interest in other areas and themes of history. The participants consider that history is not focused on in any sense, it is given in a very isolated way, and it is not fully integrated in the contents of education, but they are interested in history because, as they say, if you don't study it you are condemned to repeat it. One of the things that is repeated the most is that it does not focus on current history, and that it does not manage to give all the complete content, they only focus on some events that they consider more relevant, leaving out most of the events, and when it comes to the role of women in history, it is not even mentioned. Of all the young participants, only one person had attended a camp, and even in this camp it was mainly about historical figures, mainly men.

5.1.2. Findings on 'Level of knowledge in history'

The participants have made it clear that the way history is taught is very poorly thought out, moreover, the teaching is always biased by the person who tells it, the knowledge that is transmitted is done in a fragmented way, only focusing on students memorising dates without any common thread, leaving aside the whole historical process, moreover, the subject of history is given in a fragmented way or by blocks and recent history is not studied. As the participants commented, perhaps it would be better to try to teach it as a process and not as an event in parcels, because in the process perhaps the name of a woman appears. In the end, history is something that is alive and cannot be studied in such a static and linear way. The methodology must be changed. They also see a lack of representation of women in

textbooks and several anonymous ones, women are always invisible. The way history is taught must change so that it is not just about fulfilling the curriculum; teachers must be more involved.

Regarding female figures and male figures in history, the participants commented that their balance is very unbalanced, and that the names that came to mind were mostly men's names and this is due to the fact that this name is always repeated constantly, contrary to what happens with women's names that are omitted or not even pronounced and remain in oblivion. For some participants it was easier to remember some iconic names of women in contemporary literature, philosophers. Men's names: Dalí, Picasso, Da Vinci. Women's names: Rosa Cobo, María Zambrano, Isabela Católica, María Montessori, Simone de Beauvoir, Virginia Woolf, Clara Campoamor, Aleksandra Kolontái, Amelia Valcárcel, Andrea Durkin.

It is very important to consider the representation of all genders, women, non-binary people, and other communities, not just men. Making women's achievements visible can serve as an inspiration to young women who identify with them. Represent the full spectrum of people who contribute to and produce for history and progress to fill the gap in all fields, representing figures from the past and present in all disciplines.

Moreover, the participants consider that the erroneous representation of gender comes from the structure of the system, from the role that has been established for women as reproducers and not producers. In the end, women have always been on the margins, reduced to the private sphere, and social pressure has conditioned women's reality, making their work and achievements invisible. In addition, the gender roles or stereotypes that are adopted are conditioned by society and this leads to invisibilisation.

5.1.3. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'.

A change in methodology is important, debate and critical thinking must be promoted among students, women in history must be integrated into the curriculum, and content must be updated. There must be a change in education. The curriculum must be balanced in terms of what is taught about men and women. It cannot be that the section that talks about women is on the last page, isolated, as if it were worthless.

Women can be made visible through photographic exhibitions.

- Art, oriented towards music, theatre, building things with the hands, in individual or group work.
- Creation of audio-visual content.
- Encourage students by giving them extra points in the final assessment if they watch historical series or films and discuss them in class.
- Micro-dramas can be made, with certain historical sequences.
- Change the content or the curriculum, so that it is not always the teacher who gives the class, but the student who takes an active role in the class.
- Offer more dynamic classes.
- Encourage dynamic workshops, shock therapies.
- Role-playing games.

Collaborations

It would be interesting to do:

- Collaborations with the University of Salamanca and the UPSA, regarding the visibility of female characters.
- Collaborations with tourist guides.
- Collaboration with those who are dedicated to making micro-theatres in certain tourist areas and to make the role of women visible.
- Collaboration with public figures, influencers, etc.
- Tour the city and ask people questions about certain important female figures in the city.

Transnational map

- Add a suggestion section where you can propose a female name that has contributed to the city.
- It should be an interactive, live, dynamic map, allowing links to videos, a documentary or interactive images and, if a Twitch or TikTok channel is created, to be able to link to it. Not just mentioning dates or a timeline.
- Imagine a map full of pins, with varied information, where you can discover new characters from various fields, and not just focus on 4 of the most emblematic names.
- In addition, it would be interesting if it were very visual, with audio resources.

A map classified by areas of history, disciplines, territories that is layered, that is not told in a linear way.

Digital tools

- Social Media, create an Instagram account where you collect profiles of women throughout history, you can create smaller videos with concise information, also allow comments where other people provide more information.
- TikTok.
- Twitch channel.
- Video games.
- Create a YouTube channel.
- Short and entertaining sketches.
- Creating 5 minute pills, playing with clickbait unknowns.
- Create a podcast where you can interview different women in current history.

5.2. Martinique, France

It was difficult to find young people willing to take part in the focus group, so DA&DA created a questionnaire to gather as much information as possible on the subject.

5.2.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

First, we found that the participants' level of education and interest in history is very heterogeneous. Some have a high level of interest, others less or none. Their interest also depends on the period of history, with some periods being more interesting to them than others. Also, the history of Martinique is rarely discussed at school, as the curriculum is not adapted to and focused on metropolitan France, on Europe. It is therefore more difficult to interest young people because they do not always feel involved.

This certainly explains why most of the young people didn't participate in workshops or activities with historical content. Some participate at conferences, at documentary screenings or at events that take place on March 8th, but that's not the majority of them.

5.2.2. Findings on 'Level of knowledge in history'

The level of historical knowledge differs from one young person to another, depending on age, social background, personal interests, and studies. Their knowledge also depends on the subject, the period, etc. Furthermore, it has been noted that there is always more to learn, and that the same historical subject can be recounted differently depending on who reports and analyses it.

In any case, young people agree that the knowledge provided is not always enough. As mentioned above, one of the gaps they find is that not enough is said about Martinique's history. At school, the subjects covered are always the same, and some periods are seen several times, sometimes even every year. It's also always the same countries, regions and people that are discussed. So, there's a huge lack of information on a whole part of the world's history. Even when they do learn about the country's history, there's a part of it that's missing, since the overseas regions are neglected. Most French people don't know the history of regions like Martinique, that's why it's clear that the knowledge provided is not enough.

This lack of knowledge also applies to gender issues since all the young people agree that they know many remarkable male figures in history, but very few women. Some of them know a few French women who have contributed to history like Marie Curie, Jeanne d'Arc, Simone Veil etc., but others very few. And at the local level, knowledge is more limited and it's noticeable that some young people are not familiar with any Martinican female figure. Not all young people know the same number of remarkable women in history. Again, it depends on each person.

Most of the young people think that the representation of women in history is underestimated due to the patriarchal discourse of history. This can have a negative impact on the image that a girl or woman has of herself. However, they know that women hold a significant place in history. But the society is very patriarchal, and men focused and there is also a lack of political will in this area which explains the gender misrepresentation.

Some of the young people interviewed admit that they have never paid too much attention to the question of gender representation in history, but they still have the impression that they have heard more about men.

5.2.3. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'

According to the young people, there are different ways to promote women's footprint in history. They mainly talk about non-formal education such as games, quizzes, exhibitions and interactive activities or workshops in which people are involved and participate. Everyone agrees that it is important that people can feel integrated and be actors .

Another way to promote women's footprint in history is through culture for example books, movies, documentaries...for example the movie Hidden Figures highlights the actions of young black women and the differences that once existed. There are very few films like this one about women and they are not very known. Highlighting them and organizing screenings could raise awareness of women's contributions to history.

It's also possible to organise conferences, debates, podcasts, videos on the theme to spread portraits of women, tell their stories and raise awareness of female figures who have played an important role.

Using social networks such as YouTube, Facebook or Instagram can also help to promote women's footprint. Networks are used by everyone, and there are many features that can be used to make a publication attractive or playful enough to capture people's interest.

One of the young people gave the idea to organise a day dedicated to women in history. In general, female figures should be highlighted at cultural events but it would be easier if there were a day dedicated to these women.

School is the first place where young people encounter history, but they are not taught (or very little) about the history of some territories and the role of women. Therefore, it would be necessary to change the history and geography curriculum to include women's stories by nuancing the exploits of men who were ultimately the work of a woman in the shadows, etc.

Finally, naming streets, airports, schools, etc. after women would also help to highlight and promote remarkable feminine figures.

5.3. Nicosia, Cyprus

Two focus groups were organised involving 10 participants.

5.3.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

The participants of the focus group, despite not having deep relevance or specialisation in the field of history, displayed a strong interest in the topic. Their connection to history was mainly shaped by their experiences attending history classes during their time in high school. This foundation in history education served as a starting point for their engagement in discussions related to historical narratives and women's contributions.

5.3.2. Findings on 'Level of knowledge in history'

Within the focus group, the young participants highlighted a significant disparity between the representation of women and men in history textbooks. They emphasized that history textbooks primarily focused on male figures, leaving women significantly underrepresented both in terms of textual content and visual depictions. This exclusion perpetuated a historical narrative that marginalized and overlooked the substantial contributions of women. The participants expressed their inability to recall notable women figures from their history textbooks without resorting to external sources. Recognizing the pivotal role textbooks play in shaping their understanding, the participants underscored the urgent need for increased visibility of women's achievements in history education. They suggested that a comprehensive integration of women's stories and accomplishments into textbooks would be crucial to challenge gender stereotypes and ensure a more balanced representation of historical narratives.

5.3.3. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'

The participants exhibited enthusiasm for the proposal to create an interactive online map designed to promote awareness of women's contributions in history. They acknowledged the potency of visual representation and endorsed the inclusion of information about significant women from diverse time periods and geographical regions. This interactive map was seen as an effective tool to engage users and facilitate their exploration and learning about women's historical impact.

During discussions, the participants introduced the concept of a historical classification system or timeline. This system was suggested as a means to categorize women's contributions within specific historical contexts, aiding users in comprehending the significance of their achievements across various time periods. By showcasing women's diverse accomplishments throughout history, this approach aimed to foster a deeper appreciation for the evolution of women's roles.

Recognizing the influential role of visual media, the participants advocated for the promotion and screening of films and documentaries highlighting the stories of inspirational women. Additionally, they proposed the organisation of art exhibitions showcasing the works of both historical and contemporary female artists. These strategies were deemed effective in captivating the attention of young people while delivering impactful narratives about women's historical and cultural contributions.

Lastly, the idea of a treasure hunt as an educational activity was discussed within the focus group. This innovative approach was considered an engaging method for participants to explore cities while learning about women's history. By utilizing interactive technology, such as mobile applications, participants could navigate through specific locations, completing challenges and answering questions related to women's historical achievements. The potential inclusion of a knowledgeable guide to oversee the treasure hunt was suggested to enhance the experience by providing additional insights and guidance.

In conclusion, the focus group findings highlight the need for an overhaul in history education to rectify the gender imbalance and ensure the recognition of women's contributions throughout history. The participants' recommendations emphasize the importance of diverse educational tools, visual media, interactive technologies, and engaging activities to promote a more accurate and inclusive understanding of women's historical impact.

5.4. Athens, Greece

KEAN developed two focus groups with 9 young people.

5.4.1. 1st Focus Group with young People: Analyses and results

'Relevance with the field of History'

It seems that most of the participants didn't have a lot of interaction with History. The majority had only related to history, through school lessons. However, as they indicated, the school lessons are not very appealing for them as they learn history in a stiff and non-attractive way, trying to memorize information that they find of low relevance and use. Most of them also mentioned that the information they receive in school is not enough and is repeated through their school years. Maybe history lessons should include more information about history of other eras or other countries or other subjects.

However, participants seem to recognize the importance of history for humankind and society and refer to history as necessary to shape the future and avoid the mistakes of the past.

"It's not the history, it's the way they teach it. They force us to learn history, but if it was something we were interested in it would be much easier to learn" (Student, male, 14 years old).

" We could take from other stories, from other countries, not to put so much emphasis on the details and learn other information, other facts that will help us" (Student, male, 14 years old).

"History is essential for the smooth evolution of the human species. And I mean, if we don't have knowledge of the past, we can't know how to organise the future. It may sound a bit vague, but because there have been so many events, we have learned lessons through them, and by learning history, we know what we can avoid, what we can prefer, because through the experiences of people in history we evolve ourselves"(Student, male, 15 years old).

'Level of knowledge in history'

All the participants reported important historical information, and some of them also had knowledge about gender equality history. Regarding their level of knowledge on male figures, the participants reported more than thirty male figures in Greek history that were dominant

throughout the times. Most of these figures were heroes of the revolution against the Ottoman Empire or prime ministers of Greece the last two centuries.

"Under the Constitution of 1864, women still did not have the right to vote, only men over 21 had the right to vote. And we see how late it took for women to get the vote. That is, and what belongs to modern, recent history women didn't have it yet, which was also considered a liberal constitution." (Student, Male, 15 years old).

"I know many men from history, because they are actually dominant in history, from what we've learned at least; I know Heraclitus, Kapodistrias, Justinian and many others." (Female, Student, 16 years old).

"Kolokotronis, Miaoulis, all the heroes of the Revolution, Kapodistrias, Deligiannis, Kolletes, Venizelos..." (Female, Student, 16 years old).

The case was different regarding the knowledge of female figures, where it was more difficult to identify many of them. In that part and to support the participants, we provided different categories (science, arts, revolution, ancient Greece, sports, politics) and we asked them to think about a Greek female figure they know of the above-mentioned fields. However, they didn't manage to identify enough Greek women in all categories. Here is a summary of the females identified:

- Science: Mari Kiouri, Margaret Sanger, Jane Addams
- Arts: Frida Kahlo,
- Revolution: Bouboulina, Manto Mavrogenuous (heroes of the Greek Revolution of 1821), Roza Parks
- Ancient Greece: Hera, Afroditi, Athina (Olympian Goddesses)
- Sports: Anna Korakaki (recent Greek Olympian champion)
- Politics: Melina Merkoyri (actress and minister of culture), Maria Antouanetta,

Participants reported that the difficulty to identify Greek women in history exists probably because when a woman did something historically important, it was never reported just because of their gender. Young people supported that there were and still are stereotypes that women are lower, weak and need protection, something that needs to change because it is unfair, and we need to work towards a gender equal world.

"I remember from politics Melina Mercouri trying to return the statues that had been stolen from Greece and asking for them back, but she didn't succeed in the end." (Student, Female, 16 years old).

"Back then they gave more credit to men, so even a woman who did something very historic, maybe they didn't even put her in the books, and we don't even know her today because she was a woman" (Student, Male, 16 years old).

"I think it needs to change because a person cannot be determined by their genetic characteristics, i.e., they don't choose it, not skin color, not sexuality, not gender, not anything. A person should be distinguished by their acquired knowledge, by their education, by what they can accomplish, not by how they were born and what characteristics they have since then. That is why it must change, there should be no difference between men and women." (Student, Male, 15 years old).

'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'.

Students reported that some information should be removed from history and be replaced and enriched with more important information for all genders. Moreover, to develop and implement more interactive ways for learning history, because the goal is to learn and not just to memorize the information. Some recommendations they shared are the use of videos, quizzes, and virtual games that include information about women in history and can be used in school lessons.

Regarding the development of a transitional map, the participants imagined this to be divided with colours according to the historical era, someone is searching for. The map maybe should include not just texts of information, but also a video that presents the topic/woman that is spotted. Also, they suggested that this map should be more gamified, to provide more incentives for the young visitors. Moreover, it would be more interesting to them, if the visitor is able to add some information, he/she may know about the spot or the historical woman and the potential to communicate with a history expert.

"Let's say that when we learn about a project/fact, we should not only take into account who performed that, but who thought of it as an idea, because it is certain that it will not only be men who thought of it, but there will also be women. " (Female, 16 years old.)

"There could be a quiz app, in an interactive way, that includes pictures, videos, so that the people using it learn better." (Student, Female, 16 years old).

"If you have a map, you could click on a point on the map and it would show you at that point that some projects have been done and it would have dates and it would show you some kind of video to see and then you could answer some questions based on the map" (Student, Female, 16 years old).

"So in these maps there should be a historian, a person, like when you send to some companies, let's say, in shops and you send them a message for help; so if you have a question, you don't have to sit down to look from various sources that they are not clear; you send the message, if you have a question, a gap or say some mistakes that are on the map or put your own knowledge, something that is not on the map." (Student, Male, 15 years old).

5.4.2. 2nd Focus Group with young people: analyses and results

This focus group was held online via Microsoft Teams, on June 30, 2023. A google form was created to manage the focus group participation and 8 young people from 18-25 years old expressed their interest to participate. All of them were women. However, some dropouts were noticed, and the final focus group was realized with two members, reaching the target of 11 participants. These two participants were academic students in History-Archaeology Department, with an extensive interest in gender representation and women's empowerment.

For this focus group invitations were posted in social media and were sent in University Departments of Gender Studies, History, Social Psychology, Sociology and Human Studies.

The main findings are presented below.

'Relevance with the field of History'

Participants had a high level of relevance with history, as they were university history students. They refer to history as something essential to understand the past and shape the future. Participants refer to gender representation in history as something that we began to explore quite recently, despite the fact that they study history. That means that we must bring to surface all these gender matters.

"Is the contact you have with time and how that affects the future. Mostly I see these patterns happening and that's what fascinates me. But also, how we can ultimately be definitive in changing some things that were written into history and offer help to make changes" (Female, 21 years old).

"Because the issue of women is still in an early phase, at least in the part of history and how it is highlighted, there is still room to step in and highlight other things" (Female, 21 years old).

'Level of knowledge in history'

Both the participants had a high level of history knowledge, specializing in specific history eras, like the Byzantine or Medieval era. Participants mentioned that they can think of numerous male figures in history, while it is more difficult to identify many female figures. However, both had a high knowledge about female figures in history, from different historical eras. They attribute this inequality of gender representation to the fact that history was written exclusively by men, but also to how society and families were organised.

Some female figures that were mentioned are:

- Byzantine era: Irene of Athens
- Venetian era: Women that claim the ducats, like Margarita, that claimed the ducat of Achaia, in Greece
- Revolution of 1821: Manto Mavrogenous
- Literature: Christiana Hildegard von Bingen (German), Tatiana Gritsi-Milliex, Alki Zei, Zorz Sarri

"Because I'm more into byzantine-medieval (history), I like it more, maybe that women had a legal protection more in Byzantium than in the medieval west and we see it because we have a lot of empresses (in Byzantium)" (Female, 22 years old)

"Especially now with the 100 years of Alki Zei and Zorz Sarri, I think it's a good example" (Female, 22 years old)

"We're talking about a male-dominated space, at least that's what the history was, as it was projected, and then there's the fact of how they raised their families. I think it's very well known what I'm saying" (Female, 22 years old)

'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'

They stressed the importance of women representation in history to fight not just societal stereotypes, but also empower women to grow beside the established stereotypes. Despite the limited resources, the participants recommended that we should search for more historical resources and be more open minded towards the findings throughout history.

Some other recommendations are the enrichment of curriculums in History Departments, the creation of gender history departments in more Greek universities, and the development of seminars about gender equality in schools. They supported that education has a great role in shaping gender equality and when you add these elements in school lessons, that is when changes happen.

Moreover, the group highlighted the use of digital platforms, technology and social media are necessary, as participants support.

Regarding the development of the transnational map, the participants imagined this should be divided into categories, depending on the footprint field by each woman. Also because of the rich work of women in history, the group suggested the creation of a platform where anyone can visit a museum virtually, and all the works made by women are highlighted.

"Empowerment is not only about the man, but also about the woman. That is, it has to be somehow a simultaneous work" (Female, 22 years old)

"When you want to dig deeper into a woman's story, you fall into the gap of resources. That's a gap we can't fill, because this is work that has already been done in the past. However, what we can certainly do is to dig deeper and be more open minded to what we find" (Female, 21 years old)

"To add courses to the already existing departments" (Female, 22 years old)

"I would say that we could do some seminars in universities or some schools; we could provide some additional information so that children from an early age who are starting out in the male-dominated space can see it and distinguish it" (Female, 22 years old)

"And then of course Instagram and how we could upload some videos or upload a picture and underneath a description referring to a link or a blog where we could write" (Female, 22 years old)

"If it was about art, it could be in every museum or gallery, which works were made by women" (Female, 21 years old)

5.5. Sofia, Bulgaria

One focus group was organised, involving 10 participants.

5.5.1. Findings on 'Female and male historical figures'

The general observation of the focus group showed that names of male historical figures, especially men in power (kings, emperors, warriors, leaders, etc.) come to mind easily and without hesitation, as to, when it comes to women in history, the participants struggled to provide examples at first. When given more time to consider the question, they provided diverse examples, starting with women in art and literature, and going to sciences and women in power.

5.5.2. Findings on 'Gender Representation'

The prevailing explanation of this focus group highlights the historical absence of political and social rights for women compared to today. This disparity is the main reason behind the extensive gender misrepresentation and the noticeable gaps in historical records and student textbooks. Participants express a sense of frustration and acknowledgement of this void, considering it unfortunate that such omissions exist. Numerous women have played significant roles in shaping their respective communities and have made valuable contributions to society. It is crucial to learn about their achievements with the same level of respect given to men's accomplishments. Women are often portrayed from the perspective of others, predominantly men, be it their husbands or lovers. Regrettably, in most instances, scandals take precedence over other aspects of their lives.

5.5.3. Findings on ‘Methods to promote women’s footprint in history’

The first crucial step is to reform the education system by emphasizing the inclusion of women and their accomplishments, rather than relegating them to mere mentions as someone's wife or muse. This change is essential to ensure a more comprehensive and accurate representation of history, recognizing the significant contributions women have made throughout time. By replacing street names with those of influential women who contributed to the development of Sofia and Bulgaria, we can address the current gap in representation. Presently, the central streets of Sofia primarily bear the names of Russian generals who played roles in the Russian-Turkish war, leading to Bulgaria's liberation, along with prominent Bulgarian figures and even foreign individuals like JoliotCurie. Introducing the names of women who made significant contributions would be a meaningful step toward recognizing their impact on the city and the country.

Furthermore, the participants highlighted other successful methods they've faced before:

- In school, teachers organise quizzes, games, and screenings of both documentaries and live action movies that highlight the accomplishments of women. Additionally, students have the opportunity to engage with representatives from NGOs working in the field of feminism through organised meetings and discussions.
- Social media campaigns.
- Online games.

5.5.4. Findings on ‘Transnational HerStory map’

The participants suggested that the map should be interactive, accessible via different platforms/systems through QR-codes. It should be able to show more content (articles, photos, and most importantly – videos) when a person reaches a specific location to learn more about the woman in question.

As for the tours, the participants gave the following recommendations:

- Traditional Guided City Tour: A classic in-person city tour led by knowledgeable guides to explore the historical landmarks and cultural treasures of the city.

- **Interactive City Tour:** An in-person city tour enriched with interactive elements such as treasure hunts, quizzes, and quests, making the experience more engaging and entertaining. There should be a base version of the tour where the visitor gets to walk all locations selected, and an extended version in which they get to answer quiz questions and take part in scavenger hunts, related to the women from the map.
- **Self-Guided City Tour:** In-person city tours can be done individually, equipped with a digital map or guide and QR codes, allowing participants to explore at their own pace while still accessing valuable information.
- **Virtual City Tour:** A virtual city tour designed to accommodate people with disabilities or in case of adverse weather conditions, offering an immersive digital experience that showcases the city's highlights and historical significance.

5.6. Valenje, Slovenia

Two focus group were organised, involving 10 participants.

5.6.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

The first focus group brings together students from technical secondary schools and grammar schools. Their interest in history is mainly amateur and they have very strong opinions on the topic of the discussion, one participant was a student from University of Ljubljana.

The second focus group brought together students from different vocational and secondary schools. Some of them are more interested in history, others less so. One of the participants had previously been involved in research during her schooling on the perception of women of different ages (social roles, gender equality) in the Upper Savinja Valley and how lifestyles change over the generations.

5.6.2. Findings on 'Level of knowledge in history'

At the beginning, one of the participants first comment was, that all events are interconnected with history, and all events that are happening now are already part of the past.

During the discussion, the participants noted that their knowledge of history depends mainly on the history teachers in both primary and secondary school, who had different teaching approaches; the individual's interest in the events that happened in the past.

Regarding history as a subject in school, they think:

- That the lecturers only convey facts from history that are relevant to the ideology of the current rulers,
- That in school they learn about historical figures who are mainly important for the economic social relations of the current authorities, whereas the subject of their interest is more the research side of history,
- The focus is still on the military and political power of individuals, while the history of individuals is neglected.

When discussing why young people are not (more) interested in history, the following facts are mentioned:

- Young people have no attitude towards society in general.
- They have no awareness of belonging somewhere, they behave in a very self-centred way and are not interested in society.
- There is no collective sense of belonging.
- Economic outlook plays an important role - how to build their own career, they are not interested in others.

Above all, the general opinion of the group 1 was that interest in history could be much higher if teachers used modern teaching methods. One participant cited teaching methods used in Denmark as a way of making history more accessible to individuals by providing a variety of activities in the subject that go beyond the mere imparting of knowledge.

It is also clear from their conversation that young people have very little knowledge of local history. They do not know any woman who has influenced the environment in which they live (Šaleška dolina). They do know a woman who has left her mark on the Celje area. This is Alma M. Karlin, who was a world traveller, writer, and poet. Some of the participants visited an exhibition at the Celje Provincial Museum, which depicts her life. Participants were also

unfamiliar with women who have made and continue to make a significant contribution to the local community in which they live.

5.6.3. Female figures and male figures

During a discussion about outstanding female figures in history, it is noted that very few women have made a name for themselves. Only one of the participants mentioned a few “famous” women who have made history and are the most talked about. They believe that the reasons for the neglect of women in history are mainly because men are most often mentioned because they were known as successful warriors, warlords, leaders, while women were seen as commodities. In the 19th and 20th centuries, women were also neglected for a long time, because it was only after 1945 that they won the right to vote, after a long struggle for equality.

The reasons given for women's unequal representation include:

- religion,
- teaching in schools: men are better leaders, more aggressive, stronger,
- and men have deliberately, throughout history, removed women who have exposed themselves /were accused of being witches and so on.

But they also cite some women throughout history who have worked from behind the scenes to help men succeed.

By mentioning outstanding female personalities, they feel that only the object of research is confused (the object of research is still the EXCEPTIONAL women who have made a name for themselves, not the women who have worked within the family and the immediate environment). One participant commented that according to the economic aspect of history, women have always been involved in the functioning of society, while they have been excluded from the military and political aspects. The discussion also turns to the topic that the role of women throughout history has not always been as we imagine and learn about it today, because there are many gaps in our understanding of history. The role of women has changed a lot as society has evolved throughout history.

However, when discussing specific examples of exceptional women/men in the local area, one participant asked, "Who is an exceptional individual?" The answer of the other is that the one that most individuals agree is special. A third mentioned that it is someone who was able to do something at a crucial time, understood class developments in the current society and whose actions were in line with class developments. There are still more male than female outstanding personalities. This is mainly due to patriarchal society, which in the past, because of the inheritance of property and position through male heirs, has completely excluded women from an equal position.

For this reason, they consider it very difficult to choose criteria by which to determine whether a person deserves the title of outstanding female personality. Based on known historical facts, most women have not had the opportunity to become one, but they are very interested in the archetype of the "minor's wife", which would shed light on the role of women in the mining family. The suggestion of a 'female partisan' is also made, because during the Second World War it was not uncommon for women to go and fight in the forests. They would also like to know what role women played in the post-war reconstruction of the homeland and what mark they left. As Velenje is a relatively young city, it would also be interesting to know what Velenje was like in the socialist post-war period and what the role of women in particular was in its development.

5.6.4. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'

Methods that some of the participants have already encountered and feel would help to present history in an interesting and engaging way to young people are:

- role-playing in the school history subject
- short films about historical events
- telling stories of people who experienced the events through their own experiences
- stories through art (paintings, graffiti, etc.)
- virtual visits to exhibitions, simulations of events, etc.

When discussing the methods our participants would use to promote women who have left their mark on Slovenian history, they mainly referred to the use of mobile phone apps. It refers mainly to apps:

- Google Maps - we would add an icon:
- Landmarks / or outstanding female personalities and a short description or link to a website or short film showing the life and work of the personality,
- A mobile app (such as Pokemon GO) that can be used by different age groups, where you collect points when you visit each landmark and when you collect them all, you get a symbolic prize.

Their suggestions on how to inspire young people and introduce them to history are mainly along the following lines:

- the need to change the way education is delivered;
- organise events - readings – discussions;
- it is important to encourage research among young people;
- the project "Youth for the Development of the Šaleška Valley" was highlighted, which enables young people to present their projects in public;
- young people need to be made aware that history is not over, it is still going on and that we are all making and writing it.

How they see the herstory map tells us:

- Google Maps / Route (guided or self-guided) with a selection of important landmarks as well as important women in the environment (but it is important that there is a café in between to give you a break - similar to "Pozoj's Castle Route", or "Experience Socialism in Velenje on Youth Day").

They also mentioned that a lot of work needs to be done on content to attract young people back to the city.

5.7. Vilnius, Lithuania

Two focus groups were organised, involving 33 participants.

The schoolchildren who participated in the focus group (FG) openly shared that they do not have any particular interest in the field of history. They view it as just one of many compulsory subjects they must take at school, with little personal engagement or enthusiasm. Among all the participants, only one student clearly indicated that history lessons hold any relevance to him. This was not due to a genuine interest in the subject matter itself, but rather because he needs to pass a history exam as a requirement for his intended university studies. This lack of interest among the majority suggests that history, as it is currently taught, fails to capture the attention or imagination of most students.

It might be explained by several factors. Firstly, the education programs and teaching methods currently applied in schools may not be designed to make the subject engaging or relevant to students' lives. Traditional approaches to teaching history often rely heavily on memorization of dates and events, which can seem tedious and disconnected from the present. Secondly, teachers themselves may struggle to engage students in a way that sparks curiosity and enthusiasm. If teachers are unable to convey the importance and excitement of historical study, students are less likely to develop a genuine interest in the subject. Moreover, students show a much greater interest in contemporary history and the history of their own country, then of the wider world and other countries.

Research participants also shared that the contributions of women to history are scarcely discussed during history lessons. While they acknowledged that there had been some lessons specifically targeted at this topic, these instances were few and far between. Moreover, only a small number of participants were able to identify notable women from Lithuania's history. Instead, most of the individuals they could name were famous international figures rather than significant female historical figures from their own country.

This lack of focus on women in Lithuanian history suggests a broader issue within the curriculum, where the achievements and impact of women are not sufficiently highlighted. As a result, students are not being exposed to the rich and diverse contributions of Lithuanian women throughout history.

The participants discussed the lack of women representation in Lithuanian history, attributing it to the country's historical context and entrenched patriarchal patterns. They noted that history has traditionally been written from a male-dominated perspective, marginalizing women's contributions. Also, members of the FG emphasized the need to reevaluate and include women's significant roles to provide a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of Lithuania's past, promoting gender equality in historical representation.

Students mentioned that topics related to gender equality, social inequalities, human rights, and similar issues are rarely addressed in their curriculum. They observed that these important subjects are often overlooked or given minimal attention. Several reasons were cited for this omission.

One reason identified is the lack of teachers' competencies in these areas. Many educators may not have received adequate training or resources to effectively teach and facilitate discussions on gender equality and human rights. This gap in knowledge and skills can lead to discomfort or avoidance of these topics in the classroom.

Additionally, students pointed out that there is fear among teachers regarding the potential for different opinions on these topics to cause conflicts among students. Given the diverse perspectives that pupils may hold, particularly on issues related to gender and human rights, teachers might be concerned about managing heated debates or disagreements that could arise.

Participants of the focus group shared their opinion about the methods that could be applied to promote knowledge on women's footprint in history and to increase interest of young people in the topic:

- Apply innovative and interactive methods, including orientation games, quiz games, watching movies, initiating discussions, organising lessons outside the school, meeting people who can share their memories of the events of the past, etc.
- Provide information on the specific topic through the lens of young person, for instance, taking examples of the youth 'heroes' and relate them to the historic figures.
- Information provided on particular topic should be made concentrated with more visuals and less text.

- Interactive map could include tasks and clues that need to be solved to reach the next point of the map. It would be also motivating to get some reward after solving all clues and reaching the final point.
- One of the proposals was to combine different subjects to understand the topic deeper, e.g., history and geography, history and maths, etc.

5.8. Lecco, Italy

5.8.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

Talking about women in history, through an initial brainstorming with the students, only female figures known at a national or international level are identified (for example, Rita Levi Montalcini, Frida Kahlo, Maria Montessori, ...). However, no figures related to the specific local territory emerge. Even when prompted to reflect on streets, places, squares, monuments, and parks dedicated to local women, the students report the absence of such references.

Therefore, a subsequent investigation was conducted, partially involving the students of the institute: through the use of the internet, interviews with acquaintances, and the analysis of street maps provided by local municipalities, they sought to find publicly recognized female figures in the territory. The results confirm what the students mentioned: there are no streets, parks, monuments, or roads dedicated to local women in our regions.

Conversely, when the students were invited to explore their family history, they recounted stories and narratives of ordinary women who had the opportunity to make a difference within the community. In this way, the young people came to understand that history is not only what is studied in books but is also shaped by individual actions in their daily lives.

Thinking about history, they express a desire to talk about the present: the history they have always encountered in the classroom has focused on a distant past that they do not perceive as their own or relevant to their current life context. Instead, they insist that history can also encompass the present or recent times.

5.8.2. Findings on 'Level of knowledge in history'

The students recognize that our small local territory, compared to larger cities, makes it more challenging to find female role models, both contemporary and historical.

Therefore, the search for women's footprints has involved various approaches. The students have interviewed family members and acquaintances of different ages, contacted mayors to access local street maps, conducted research through the internet, and consulted books and

territorial guides. From all these sources, the total absence of recognized and publicly appreciated local women becomes evident.

5.8.3. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'

The students, invited to reflect on effective methods of promoting women's footprints in our territory, identify the following strategies.

One key tool is the use of various communication channels. Through mass media, it is possible to highlight narratives and give voice to stories and women's footprints, reaching populations of different ages and locations. Within these women's stories, a source of inspiration for the future, shared interests, and points of connection between generations can be found.

Art can also be employed as a means to address the theme. The students cite an example from the Municipality of Bellano, where 1700 inhabitants were captured in photographs displayed throughout the streets of the town, preserving their faces for the future. Building on this concept, the students envision a specific version of this initiative focused on valuing female figures from the local territory.

Furthermore, everyone can think of themselves as artists by creating drawings, poems, and songs through which they can express their interpretation of the theme and the importance of Her Story.

Finally, for the young students, it is essential to have concrete opportunities to meet these women. They recount how what they read in history books often feels distant from their own experiences. Therefore, having the chance to get to know local figures offers a tangible opportunity for knowledge and exchange.

6. Women's footprint in history around European cities

6.1. Salamanca, Spain

As Pérez-Lucas (1989) ²⁹ mentions, a Salamanca woman is anyone who, whether or not she was born in Salamanca, just because she has spent most of her life there and has played a leading role, has the right to be considered as such.

Salamanca is a city full of stories carried out by women: some focused on power, literature, science, those who fought for the city, those who have given their lives to the spiritual exercise of religious life and popular women such as craftswomen, among many others.

Mujeres Vacceas. In 220 B.C., the Vacceas abandoned the passive role assigned to them and proved their courage by taking up the fight and defending their city.

Doña Urraca y Doña Mafalda. Doña Urraca and her husband were assigned the task of repopulating Salamanca. Furthermore, on her father's death, Alfonso VI, the Kingdom was left in her hands. On her remarriage to "El Batallador", they were proclaimed kings of León and Castile. Mafalda died in Salamanca and is buried in the Old Cathedral, next to the main altarpiece presided over by Virgen de la Vega, patron saint of the city.

Beatriz Galindo. Latin teacher at Isabela Católica. She created several foundations: The Santa Cruz Hospital, monasteries such as the Franciscan-Conceptionist monasteries and the Conception Hieronymite monastery.

Feliciana Enríquez de Guzmán. She defied society by dressing as a man in order to study at university. She graduated with a degree in canons, becoming a well-known Spanish poet and playwright.

Dolores Cebrián Fernández Villegas. She was born in Salamanca and was the daughter of a military man from Salamanca, a doctor and university professor. She studied to be a teacher and later became a teacher in Salamanca, a post she later resigned to become a professor of science in Toledo.

²⁹ M. D. Pérez-Lucas, Singular Women from Salamanca (220 A.C.-Siglo XIX). Amaru, 1989.

Santa Teresa de Jesús. Honorary doctorate from the University of Salamanca. The first woman to be awarded a doctorate by the Catholic Church. She wrote prose, poetry and short stories. She had a profound and analytical vision.

Matilde Cherner. She was a writer and journalist. She signed with the masculine name "Rafael de Luna". She was concerned with social issues and the role of women in society.

Carmen Martín Gaité. Philology student, professionally successful, an award-winning writer in the history of Spanish literature.

María del Rosario López Piñuelas. She is a Spanish actress who, as a student of Philosophy and Literature, participated in several plays. She later studied at the Escuela Oficial de Cine (Official Film School). She worked in theatre and televisión.

Helena Pimenta. She is a Spanish stage director, playwright and theatre director. She studied English and French Philology at the University of Salamanca.

“La brava”: **Doña María Rodríguez de Monroy.** Born in Plasencia, but settled in Salamanca, María Rodríguez de Monroy, known as María la Brava, dazzles in history for her role in the conflict of the struggles between noble families in the capital of Salamanca in the middle of the 15th century.

Doña Gonzala Santana: **“La polilla de Oro”.** A woman who, despite being wealthy, chose to remain single, a rare occurrence in her time. She dedicated her life to helping the most needy, donated money to construct a school and created scholarships for the poorest children. She is one of the benefactors of the Vera Cruz brotherhood.

Female governors of Salamanca

- **Doña Berenguela I of Castile:** (1180-1246) daughter of Alfonso VIII and Leonor of England, she was known as "The Great" for her political vision and very fair in her actions. She was proclaimed Queen at the Cortes of Valladolid and resigned in favour of her son Ferdinand III. This woman achieved the definitive union of the kingdoms of Castile and León.

- Doña María de Molina: (1260-1321) is also a clear example of the great political work that some women undertook. She was recognised by the people and respected by the monarchy of the time.
- Doña María de Portugal: She was an innovative woman and dictated a rule that affected all women: women from Salamanca would not be obliged to answer for the debts of their husbands.
- Queen Juana Manuel de Villena: She was governor of Salamanca from 1369 to 1381 due to her marriage to Enrique de Trastámara, who became king of Castile after defeating his brother Pedro I "The Cruel". During the war she actively supported her husband. As King of Castile, Juana led the siege of Zamora, which was surrendered in 1373.
- Doña Leonor de Aragón: (1358-1382) was Lady of Salamanca for one year, a position she held when her husband, Juan I, succeeded her father Enrique II of Trastámara in 1379. Her death in 1382 endangered peace between Aragon and Castile.
- Doña María de Aragón (1396-1445) became governor of Salamanca in 1440-1445, married to King Juan II. During these years the city, like the rest of the kingdom, was at loggerheads between the detractors and supporters of Álvaro de Luna, the King's chief adviser. In an attempt to defuse these clashes, the King handed over the government of the city to his wife, who tried to mediate between the two sides, but her untimely death frustrated his efforts.

Las Freiras Comendadoras de Sacti-Spiritus. Women of the nobility. They fought to defend their privileges against the Grand Master of Santiago.

Las Emparedadas. The Emparedadas, women locked in cells in the walls of the churches, although it is said that they were dedicated to visiting the sick, making clothes and liturgical clothes for the offices.

La Negrita. A woman famous for having the gift of prophecy and for performing miracles.

Romana "La Merenguera". A woman who filled the lives of the people of Salamanca with joy, representing the craftswomen who were great entrepreneurs in the city.

María Teresa Vicente Mosquete. Geographer and Honorary Professor of the master's degree in interdisciplinary Gender Studies at the University of Salamanca.

María de Maeztu. She was one of the first women officially enrolled as a student at the University of Salamanca. She was a disciple of Miguel de Unamuno. She is linked to the promotion of equality through education and to the commitment to a fairer and more caring society through a life dedicated almost entirely to the fight against illiteracy, to the universalisation of reading, to the education of women, to the establishment of coeducation for girls and boys, to the reinforcement of humanistic values in the classroom.

Lucía de Medrano. The story of Lucía de Medrano reflects the intellectual atmosphere of the time: the liberal and humanist thought of the University. In the midst of the shadows of the Middle Ages, the lights of Humanism gradually appeared, demanding a change in the role of women in society and the characters of women like Lucía de Medrano at the University of Salamanca.

María Telo Núñez. The woman who achieved, still under Franco's regime, the reform of the Civil Code in 1975 by which the so-called "Marital Licence" and "Obedience" to the husband were abolished.

Ana Díaz Medina. Dr. Ana Díaz Medina was a Professor of History at the University of Salamanca. For more than four decades and until her retirement, she developed a valuable teaching and research activity at the University of Salamanca. Since 2002, she has been director of the Centre for Women's Studies at the University of Salamanca (CEMUSA). From the Centre she promoted numerous activities and initiatives. One of these initiatives was the CEMUSA journal: *Multidisciplinary gender studies - Estudios multidisciplinares de género*.

Magdalenas Garretas Sastre. Degree in Philosophy and Letters in 1934. Graduated with an Extraordinary Prize. Assistant to Unamuno, she later became a Greek Language and Literature lecturer. She became a secondary school teacher and taught until her retirement in 1982.

6.2. Martinique, France

In Martinique, women's footprint is rarely highlighted. The society is very misogynistic and the relations between women and men in the society are unequal, with a dominance of the

male gender. In Fort-de-France, for example, the capital of Martinique, there are only 14 streets named after women which shows the low presence of women on the island. A woman's street was even renamed after a man after the street was relocated.

Although we don't talk about it much, many Martinican women have played crucial roles in various fields, leaving a positive impact and imprint in history. Women in Martinique have been leaders, activists, educators, artists, entrepreneurs, and caregivers, among many other roles.

Historically, women have been at the forefront of social movements, fighting for civil rights, labour rights, and gender equality. They have been active participants in shaping the political landscape and advocating for important societal changes.

In the fields of arts and culture, women in Martinique have been influential in literature, music, dance, and visual arts, enriching the island's cultural heritage and promoting its unique identity. Writers such as Aimé Césaire and Édouard Glissant have achieved international recognition, but the contributions of women writers and artists have often been under-represented. Women like Suzanne Roussi-Césaire and Mayotte Capécia have made important literary contributions that reflect the experiences and perspectives of Martinican women.

Additionally, women have been pivotal in the economic development of Martinique through entrepreneurship and leadership in various industries.

It is essential to recognize and celebrate the significant contributions of Martinican women and to continue promoting gender equality, empowering women, and ensuring that their voices are heard and valued in all aspects of society. By acknowledging and appreciating their footprint, we can build a more inclusive and equitable future for Martinique.

Below you can find female figures that left their mark in Martinique:

Jane Léro (1916-1961) was a Martinican activist and feminist. She is known for her advocacy for women's rights and the promotion of gender equality in Martinique. She founded *l'Union des Femmes de la Martinique* (UFM), the first feminist organisation.

She is a significant figure in the social and political movements in Martinique during the 1940s and 1950s. Jane Léro also participated in local feminist movements and was a vocal advocate

against gender inequalities and social injustices. She played an important role in raising awareness about the specific issues faced by Martinican women at that time and her work contributed to paving the way for future advancements in the fight for gender equality in the society.

Lumina Sophie also called Surprise (1848-1879) was a Martinican activist and poet. She was an advocate for women's rights, education, and workers' rights. Surprise used her poetry to address social and political issues, and she was an influential figure in the cultural and political spheres of Martinique. She spoke out against the segregation and racism that persisted in Martinique after the abolition of slavery and took part in the southern insurrection of September 1870. She was arrested a few days later. After two trials, she was sentenced to forced labour for life. After giving birth in prison, she was transferred to the penal colony of Guyana where she died on December 15th, 1879.

Suzanne Roussi-Césaire (1915-1966), born in Martinique, was a writer, poet, anti-colonial and feminist activist and cultural figure. She co-founded the literary journal "Tropiques" (1941-1945) with her husband Aimé Césaire, providing a platform for Caribbean intellectuals and artists. Like many women in history, Suzanne Césaire has been overshadowed by the fame of her husband. Her ideas have not only been poorly read and rarely analyzed but have also been sometimes wrongly attributed. For example, in the article she published in 1948 in *Présence africaine* about the novel *Je suis martiniquaise*, by Mayotte Capécia, Jenny Alpha wrongly attributes Suzanne Césaire's aesthetic decree "La poésie martiniquaise sera cannibale ou ne sera pas" to Aimé Césaire³⁰. Furthermore, often racialized and exoticized, Suzanne Césaire has essentially been associated with the status of Aimé Césaire's wife. However, Suzanne Césaire is the author of a work that has been overlooked for too long but is essential to the literary history of the Caribbean.

The Nardal sisters were significant figures in the intellectual and cultural movement of Négritude in Martinique and France. They played a key role in recognizing and valorizing black culture and identity, as well as fighting against racism and social injustices. Their literary

³⁰ Philippe Triay. *Encore peu connue, l'œuvre de Suzanne Césaire décryptée par l'universitaire Anny-Dominique Curtius*, in Martinique la 1^{ère} France Télévision, 22 janvier 2021, <https://la1ere.francetvinfo.fr/encore-peu-connue-l-uvre-de-suzanne-cesaire-decryptee-par-l-universitaire-anny-dominique-curtius-915133.html>

works, editorial activities, and political engagement had a significant influence on raising awareness of the history and contributions of black people in the francophone world. They paved the way for many other writers and intellectuals who continued to explore and celebrate the diversity and richness of black culture.

Paulette Nardal (1896-1985) was a writer, poet, and feminist. She arrived in Paris in 1920 and enrolled at the Sorbonne University to study English. She became the first black woman to study at this French institution. She co-founded the literary journal "La Revue du Monde Noir" in Paris in the 1920s, which served as a platform for black intellectuals and inspired Afro-feminism and, more broadly, intersectional feminism. Paulette Nardal wrote essays and articles that contributed to the emergence of Négritude as a literary and political movement. But like many women, her ideas and contributions have been overshadowed or attributed to men. In a letter to biographer Senghor, Paulette wrote: "*Césaire and Senghor took up the ideas we brandished and expressed them with much more sparkle - we were only women! We paved the way for men*".³¹

Jeanne Nardal (1902-1993) was also a major figure of the Négritude movement. She contributed to the creation of the journal "Légitime Défense" in Paris in the 1930s, which promoted black culture and ideas. Jeanne Nardal used her writing to denounce racism and social inequalities while encouraging pride and appreciation of African culture.

Andrée Nardal (1910-1935) was also involved in the Négritude movement but is primarily known for her role as a teacher and educator in Martinique. She founded a private school that played a significant role in spreading Négritude ideas and promoting education among young Martinicans.

Manon Tardon (1913-1989) is a prominent figure of the French Resistance and the Free France movement. During the Second World War, she joined the army and attended the General Delattre de Tassigny School for Officers. She became a specialist in the Women's Division of the Army (Arme Féminine de l'Armée de Terre), first at the rank of aspirant, and

³¹ BERTIN-ELISABETH, C. (2021). Les Nardal : Textes, co-textes, contextes. *Fédérer Langues, Altérités, Marginalités, Médias, Éthique*, (1). <https://doi.org/10.25965/flamme.89>

later promoted to an officer and lieutenant. She actively participates in various resistance networks of Free France and was decorated with the “Croix de Guerre of Free France”³².

Luce Lemaistre (1912-2000) was Martinique's first female mayor. She was elected in 1949 in the new commune of Morne-Vert. Although her term was not long (2 years), at that time it was something important as women had just obtained the right to vote (in 1944). Indeed, the women’s right to vote took a long time to be established. There have been revendications for a long time, but it wasn't until 1944 that the cause was heard. These claims have been particularly advocated by some women like the "Dames de Tivoli", **Camille Fitte-Duval** and **Césaire Rosamond**, who organised a conference on the subject in 1925. But there were also women like Irma Cécette, Claude Carbet and Paulette Nardal who helped women win the right to vote.

Jenny Alpha (1910-2010) was a Martinican woman who left her mark on the history of creole music. She was a singer and an actress and appeared in more than a hundred theatre productions and movies. In the post-war period, she was an activist for the recognition of Creole culture as part of the Négritude movement. She has made a major contribution to French culture.

6.3. Nicosia, Cyprus

Faneromeni School. The Ottoman period in Cyprus was during 1571 – 1878. During the last decades of the Ottoman period in Cyprus, primary education began to develop in the Orthodox community of the island. Faneromeni School was founded in this context, which was the first primary school for girls in Cyprus. The school was intended for the daughters of the wealthy families of the Greek Cypriot community and was founded on the initiative of Archbishop Makarios I in 1859.

The general situation for Girls Schools in Cyprus was as follows: In Limassol, the first Girls School was founded in 1911, the second in 1923, and the third in 1938. In Larnaka, the Girls School – *Parthenagogio Skalas* and Evryviadion Girls School – *Parthenagogio Evryviadion* were merged in 1906 and separated again in 1929. In Pafos, a Girls School was established in

³² In English : War cross 1939-1945. It's a French military decoration to honor people who fought with the Allies during World War II.

1880. In Famagusta, a Girls School was established in 1887 and in 1926 it was divided into two schools, the second of which operated until 1941. In Kyrenia, the Girls School was opened in 1887 (Michailidou 2017).³³

Regarding Faneromenis School, during its first year 35 female students were studying in all six classes of the school. Twenty years later, in 1880, the School had 152 female students and it was the only school for female students in Nicosia. During its first years the classes were reading, writing, mathematics, religion classes, Greek history classes and handcraft classes. Female students learned the values that a girl should follow in order to compromise with society's values. Such values were modesty, care, diligence and obedience.

Back at that time, women were considered ashamed to work. Because of that, the school committee used to give scholarships to girls with fewer opportunities and from poor villages. In this way, they gave them the opportunity to be educated in order to become teachers.

Inside Faneromeni's School the first higher institution for female teachers was established back in 1903. Female teachers used to be paid less than male teachers and also, married female teachers weren't allowed to work and they were obligated to stop working as teachers when they were planning to get married.

The Higher institution was shut down in 1937 and the building was a part of the Pancyprian Highschool institute which welcomed only female students. In 1975, was the only year that the school was a mixed-gender school. Back then, directress and female teachers of Faneromeni's School, had a crucial involvement in the development of women's associations. One example was Theano Parouti – Liasidou, who was a directress of the School from 1887 until 1901. Later she quitted because she was about to get married, and Eleni Christou was placed as a directress of the school. Some years later, in 1914, they managed to create a women's association in Nicosia.

In recent years Faneromeni's school had a kindergarten, primary school, and high school. Now, it works as a department of the School of Architecture of the University of Cyprus.

Anna Tiggidou, the first female scientist in Cyprus³⁴. Anna Tiggidou was studying in Faneromeni's School. It is said that Anna Tiggidou is the first Cypriot female scientist. Anna was born in Lefkara (Larnaka) and she Dentistry at the "Ecole Dentaire de Paris" (School of

³³ Michaelidou, M. (2017). Girls Education in Cyprus.

³⁴ Find online: <https://larnakaonline.com.cy/2016/02/22/25297/>

Dentistry of Paris). When she completed her studies in France, she ended up in Larnaka where she had her own dental office.

Ourania Kokkinou Statue³⁵. Next to the entrance of the school is one of the few statues in Nicosia dedicated to a woman. It represents Ourania Kokkinou, the first female theologian in Cyprus. She was also a directress of the Pancyprian Female Gymnasium in the Kykkos area. She was a member of EOKA and was imprisoned for her activities.

The Royal Hall. The Royal Hall used to be one of the first cinemas in Nicosia until the end of the 40s. Today, the same building is being used as an event venue.

On the 25th of April 1955, the Pancyprian Protest of Female Workers took place there and the protest was about social security and for a better working environment. In the announcement, they were mentioning the right to be absent from work when sick, the security of the widows and orphans, and equal payment between men and women.

On the 9th of July 1959, there was another crucial event in this place. The founding conference of the Pancyprian Federation of Women's associations took place there. At this conference there were 1500 female participants from around Cyprus. This conference was about the right of vote for women, for equal rights between men and women in social and political life, for social security, for legislative security of mothers and children, for equal payment between men and women, for whole education and professional skills of children, for the security of all female workers, and for a peaceful and independent Cyprus.

Xanthis Xenierou Avenue. The Royal Hall is located in Xanthis Xenierou Avenue. Xanthis Xenierou Avenue is one of the few avenues which is named after a female figure. Xanthis Xenierou is the refined creation of Elisabeth Santi-Lomaca, who was a thinker of Cypriot descent. She was married to the French Ludovico Senié and she moved to Paris and died there in 1808. She is a famous highbrow woman known for "Literary Saloons" and the mother of the French poet André Chénier.

The "Literary Saloons" were the houses of educated women who invited different highbrow people in meetings for sharing ideas and communication. These women, named as

³⁵ Find online: <https://www.bigcyprus.com.cy/el/destinations/nicosia/mnimeio-oyranias-kokkinoy-sti-leykosia>

“salonnières”, helped in the diffusion of the Enlightenment Ideas when these Ideas were still prosecuted by the French authorities.

The well-known figures of the Enlightenment such as Voltaire and Rousseau, were believers of the idea that women belonged to the private sector and were unable to participate in the public sphere and in politics. Thus, even though women were part of diffusing the Enlightenment ideas and in the French revolution, it is known that the revolution denied their participation in politics by voting and later on, in 1793, the revolutionary government preached every female political action.

The Shelter for working women. The Shelter for working women, has been located in Sokratous 19th Avenue since 1960. Anastasia Koumbaridou had the idea for this initiative, since the women that worked in the area were coming from rural areas and they didn't have any place to rest during their break from work.

Anastasia Koumbaridou, asked from the Faneromenis Church to give this place to women for this purpose. Back then, there were beds and other facilities and up to 75 women were having a place to relax and eat during their work-break times. Also, it was also a place where female workers and their trade unions had the opportunity to meet and talk about any working issues. Today, the Shelter is still working but not in the same dynamic as the earlier years.

Women's Bazaar – 'ginekopazaro'. Back in the time, women were gathering at the end of Ledras Street to sell their own products. There you could find women from all over Cyprus, from the villages and the rural areas. This was a way of survival back then. Women were getting there using their donkeys and they were sitting on the floor with the stuff they made. Some of the selling goods were hand-woven textile, silk textiles and cotton. All these were handcrafts by the women. We don't really know the exact time that the '*Ginekopazaro*' started, however, there are some clues that this was happening even from the Franks period (13th – 15th century). Then, during the early years of the 20th century, the women's bazaar was a crucial part of Nicosia's bazaars.

In 1922, the Faneromeni's Church Committee decided to build a specific place to host the women's bazaar. This was an initiative in order to protect the women from the sunny and/or the rainy days. The new women's bazaar was launched in 1924 at the end of Ledras Street.

'Ginekopazaro' stopped working in June, 1958 because of the British Colony and the restrictions of that period. In 1969 this building was demolished. However, in 2008, the 'ginekopazaro' was renewed in a more modern way, back at the place when the first women's bazaar was taking place (at the place where the Büyük Hamam is nowadays). This was an initiative of Amvrosia's Sakkadas, who had also a shop in Ledras Street and she came up with this idea to motivate people to reach this area more.

Ledras Street – Loukia Nikolaidou, the first female artist in Cyprus³⁶. Ledras Street is a major shopping street in central Nicosia. Around Ledras Street, Loukia Nikolaidou, the first female painter in Cyprus, had one of her first exhibitions in 1934. Loukia Nikolaidou, was the first female painter that studied Art abroad. She was born in 1909 in Limassol and died in 1994, at Penn in England. Back in the time, she decided to go abroad, in Paris and study Art.

During that time, that was a very brave decision since decisions like that were not aligned with what the society would expect from Loukia to do. Societal stereotypes and gender norms would expect Loukia to stay at home and start her own family.

She studied in Paris at the Colarossi Academy and then she continued to the School Nationale Superieure des Beaux-Arts. She came back to Cyprus in 1933 and she made her first three exhibitions, both in Nicosia and Limassol. The exhibition in Nicosia, was around Ledras Street, the exact location is unknown. The exhibitions were in 1934, 1935 and 1936. Later on, she continued with other great and famous exhibitions both personal and in collaboration with other famous artists.

In 1992, there was an exhibition dedicated to her work at the National Gallery in Nicosia.

'Aischilou' Avenue. This avenue is an opportunity to learn about women and theatre in Nicosia. From the one side of this Avenue is the back aspect of the Faneromenis' School and on the other is the place where the Papadopoulo's Theatre used to be.

Back in the time, in the 40s, women actors were a big taboo for that period. Male actors were playing even the female roles. In 1891, there was the first time that a Cypriot woman actor was playing in the theatre scene. This girl was Polixeni Fisentzidi, a student of the

³⁶ Find online: <https://www.philenews.com/politismos/article/548024/i-protoporos-loukia-nikola%CE%90dou/>

Faneromeni's Female School. The next years were more theatrical acts from both female and male students.

The Papadopoulo's Theatre was in this Avenue from 1899 until 1967. It was the most valuable theatre of Nicosia and there were a lot of theatrical acts in which female actors were participating, both from abroad and Cyprus. Unfortunately, in 1967 the owners decided to demolish it in order to build shops.

**Faneromeni's School, Ourania Kokkinou Statue, The Royal Hall, Xanthis Xenierou Avenue, The Shelter for working women, Women's Bazaar, 'Aischilou' Avenue, are places discovered after the research of the Centre for Gender Equality and History, in 2016, in the concept of a tour with the name "Reviving the invisible history of women: A walk in another Nicosia" (Oct. 2016)*

Zena Palace – Theognosia Zena Kanther³⁷. Zena Palaca is one of the first cinemas that existed in Cyprus, located in the center of Nicosia. It took its name from its owner, Princess Zena Kanther De Tyras, who was born in Tala, Paphos, on July 3, 1927, in a poor family. In 1967, Zena Kanther, after being spiritually adopted by Prince Paul Palaiologos-Krive, acquired a noble title, and became "Princess de Tyras." Since then, along with the enormous wealth she gained from her marriage to the American millionaire Christian Kanther, Zena Kanther has been actively involved in significant philanthropic activities. She is the most prominent Cypriot philanthropist and benefactor of Cyprus, who also volunteered in the liberation struggle against the British

Lady of Lapithos Euphrosyne Proestou³⁸. During the Turkish invasion on August 6, 1974, 12 soldiers were cut off and trapped behind enemy lines. These soldiers were discovered by a 74-year-old woman named Euphrosyne Proestou at that time. She hid them in a small cave near her home and took care of them for an entire month, all while evading the watchful eyes of the numerous Turkish forces already present in Lapithos. The Turks became suspicious of her actions and started interrogating her. She endured horrific torture. They stripped her, tied her behind a military jeep, and dragged her on the asphalt until her skin turned crimson from the wounds and blood. Despite the severe mistreatment, she didn't utter a word. When she passed away in 1993 at the age of 90, her 12 "adopted" soldiers, as she considered them her

³⁷ Find online: <https://www.cyprusalive.com/el/princess-zena-kanther-de-tyras>

³⁸ Find online: <https://www.philenews.com/kipros/koinonia/article/1373529/martiria-gia-tous-12-ethnofrouous-pou-diesose-i-kira-tis-lapithou/>

children, erected a monument in her honor in front of the Ledra Palace, overlooking the enslaved Pentadaktylos mountain range.

Liberty Monument. The Liberty Monument was erected in 1973 to honor the fighters of EOKA during the Cyprus Liberation Struggle of 1955-1959. It is located within the Venetian walls. The grand monument contains several statues. At the top of the structure, a statue represents the "Clocks of Freedom" above two heroic EOKA fighters opening the chains to unlock the prison gate, allowing Greek Cypriot captives, farmers, and clergy to escape from British rule. The bronze figures of men and women of different ages are vividly depicted emerging from the darkness of the prison after a long time and witnessing the light of day. The fact that the official inauguration for this monument never took place due to the tragic events of 1974 is a poignant irony. Just when the Cypriot Hellenism saw the light of the sun after a long time and was heading towards the ultimate good of freedom, the violent Turkish invasion suddenly overturned their hopes. The monument becomes a timeless symbol of struggle and hope for freedom.

Elpinikis Street. The street "Elpinikis" in Nicosia took its name from Elpiniki, who was an ancient Greek woman from Sicily and the Cypriot city of Salamis. She is known for her contribution during the Trojan War, as she provided significant financial support to the Greek warriors who fought against Troy. The choice of the street's name may have been made to honor the mythical or historical figure of Elpiniki and to highlight the cultural richness of ancient Greece and Cyprus.

Arsinoyis Street. The Arsinoyis Street took its name from Arsinoyi, a historical figure from ancient Cyprus. Arsinoyi was the wife of King Leontokrates of Cyprus during the Ptolemaic dynasty. Also known as Arsinoyi II, she was the queen of Cyprus in the 3rd century BCE and had significant influence in the political and cultural affairs of that era. During her reign, she conducted numerous excavations and projects to improve Cypriot society. The street that bears her name recognizes the importance of Arsinoyi in the history of Cyprus and the Ptolemaic period, while also honoring her contributions to ancient Cypriot culture.

Σωματείο Ελληνίδων Κυριών Μάνα / 'Somatio Ellinidon Kirion Mana'. The Association was founded in March 1933 by a group of women with the purpose of philanthropy and care for mothers and children. As part of its contribution, the Association has been diligently

supporting working mothers through the establishment of nurseries and canteens and continues to do so until today.

Pancyprian Federation of Women's Organisations. The "Pancyprian Federation of Women's Organisations" is an organisation founded in Cyprus at the year of 1959 with the aim of promoting women's rights and empowering women's voices and participation in society. The Pancyprian Federation of Women's Organisations operates throughout Cyprus and collaborates with various women's organisations and communities on the island. The Pancyprian Federation of Women's Organisations organises events, conferences, seminars, and educational programs to raise awareness among the public about issues concerning women and to promote gender equality. Additionally, it cooperates with other entities and organisations to achieve its goals in advocating for women's rights in Cyprus.

Eleftheria Square. Eleftheria Square is a central square located in Nicosia. It is one of the most well-known and vibrant areas of the city, serving as a hub for social, cultural, and commercial activities. Freedom Square boasts impressive architecture with various buildings and monuments surrounding it. It is a beloved destination for both locals and tourists, where they can enjoy the hospitality of the Cypriot capital, go shopping, savor local cuisine, and experience the liveliness of the old city around them. Additionally, the square often hosts various events, exhibitions, musical performances, and festivals, offering a unique experience to its visitors.

Kostas and Rita Severis Foundation. The "Kostas and Rita Severis Foundation" is a philanthropic organisation founded in Cyprus with the aim of promoting arts, culture, and education. The foundation was established by Kostas and Rita Severis, two prominent Cypriot philanthropists, who dedicated their lives to the promotion of the country's artistic and cultural heritage. The foundation operates as a cultural centre and advocates various initiatives to support and develop Cyprus' artistic community. It offers scholarships and financial support to young artists, promotes exhibitions, theatrical events, musical performances, and facilitates cultural programs and events for the public. Additionally, the Kostas and Rita Severis Foundation manages and preserves cultural landmarks and historic buildings in Cyprus, thus promoting the heritage and cultural legacy of the region. The

foundation constitutes a significant contribution to Cyprus' cultural and artistic life and fosters artistic creation and culture in the area.

Catherine Cornaro. Catherine Cornaro was the Queen of Cyprus and the wife of Peter I of Cyprus. Their marriage took place in 1382, and she became the Queen of Cyprus. Peter I and Catherine ruled the kingdom with dignity and success, strengthening Cyprus' relations with neighboring countries and promoting the prosperity of its people. After Peter I's death in 1392, Catherine continued to govern Cyprus as the Queen Mother for their son, James II. However, in 1398, James II removed Catherine from power and exiled her to Sicily, where she passed away at around the age of 60. Catherine Cornaro was known for her kindness and love for the people of Cyprus. Her reign marked a period of prosperity and cultural development for the Cypriot people.

Diamantou Charalambous. Women's footprint in all the efforts of changing the working conditions in Cyprus, was decisive. Back in the days, women were active in trade unions and fought under extremely difficult conditions towards a more human working environment and for better income and for working rights.

In the strike struggles of the silk factory of Geroskipou in 1927, the spinning mill P. Ioannou in Famagusta in 1938, in the bunches of the Limassol and Larnaca factories in 1942 and 1945 respectively, in the mines of Mavrovounio-Xeros and Asbestos in 1948, in the sectors of clothing, footwear, construction and agriculture and in so many others in the 1950s and 1960s, women gave their "presence" en masse, militantly, worthily and exemplarily.

During this period Cyprus was under British Colonial. Back on these years, Cyprus were a place of constant strikes and demands for change. Diamantou Charalambous was a construction worker in May 1940. This was something really revolutionary for the social norms of those years. Diamantou combatted all gender stereotypes and refused to respond to any of the gender norms that wanted women to stay in the private sphere, as good mothers and good housewives.

In May 1940 Diamantou Charalambous took part in a demonstration of unemployed construction workers in Nicosia. She was savagely beaten by the police for taking part in this demonstration, in which the workers demanded that the colonial government open jobs for

the unemployed. Unfortunately, there aren't any date for the exact place that this took place. However, the first trade unions were located at Metaksa Square, as the Eleftheria Square used to be called.

Marika Kotopouli Street. Marika Kotopouli, one of the most important figures of modern Greek theatre, was born in Athens on 3 May 1887 to theatrical parents, Dimitrios and Eleni Kotopouli. Although a Greek figure, her descent to Cyprus in 1927 is one of the most important moments in the history of Cypriot theatre, which was warmly welcomed by journalists, poets, people of the arts and letters. In the centre of Nicosia, there is Marika Kotopouli Street.

Marika Kotopouli began her theatrical career in 1897 with her parents' company, performing outside Athens. In 1902 she joined Christomanos' "New Stage", but quickly moved to the "Royal Theatre of Athens". In 1906 she travelled to Paris with her cousin, actor Petros Nikolaou.

Her career began in 1908, when she formed a company with the comedian Konstantinos Sayor. In 1911, she founded a new company with the comedian Ioannis Papaioannou, presenting Hofmannsthal's Elektra at the Attikon. In 1912, she formed her first personal company and acquired her own theatrical home, the "Marika Kotopouli Theatre", in Omonia Square.

In 1921, she was awarded the Golden Cross of George I and in 1923, she received the Award of Arts and Letters from the Ministry of Education. In 1937, after the abandonment of the "Theatre Kotopouli", he founded the "Rex" on Panepistimiou Street, presenting the play "Elizabeth" by André José. In 1939, the thirty-year anniversary of her thirtieth anniversary was celebrated and her company became a semi-public company.

During the Occupation, she retired from theatrical performances and helped several of her leftist colleagues. She belonged to the right and supported royalty. After liberation, she was appointed chairman of the artistic committee and a member of the board of directors of the National Theatre, which was renamed the Royal Theatre after the restoration of royalty in 1946.

Marika Kotopouli died suddenly of cardiac arrest in Athens on 11 September 1954, at the age of 67.

Axiotheas' Street. Axiothea was an ancient heroine of Cyprus, wife of Nicocles, the last descendant of the dynasty of the Kiniraid. In the 4th century BC, when the Egyptian king Ptolemy I invaded with his army and captured Nicocles' palace, causing his death, his wife, Aξιοthea, chose to commit suicide rather than suffer the humiliation of captivity.

Thus, when Sesshea learned of Nicocles' death, she called upon all the women of the palace not to tolerate the disgrace and fall into the hands of their enemies. And as none of their opponents conquered, the women closed and barricaded the women's room and went up to the roof of the palace. There, before the eyes of the assembled multitude, Merithea slaughtered her unmarried daughters, and the wives of Nicocles' brothers followed her example, slaughtering their own children. Then they set fire to the thatched roof and some committed suicide by falling into the flames and others with swords. The last to commit suicide was Aξιοthea, giving a sword to herself and jumping into the fire, lest the opponents keep a dead body. Nicocles' brothers, after all these evils, set fire to the palace and were themselves slain.

6.4. Athens, Greece

Despite these prevailing gender norms in Athens throughout its history, there were instances of women who held exceptional roles or gained power and influenced Greek society by utilizing their family network. Throughout history plenty of fights and sacrifices happened by women who left their mark in Greek society, in different aspects like art, science, culture, revolution and human rights.

Herstory Focus groups and research brought to surface a lot of different women throughout Greek history and their importance. Nevertheless, because of the limited monuments or dedicated places for their achievements, only specific women were selected to be presented at Herstory (some widely known, some unknown), where information and monuments of them can be found in Athens. These women are presented below.

Sappho (630-570 BC) the Greek lyric poet. Besides the sculptures of her in Lesvos, there is a brass statue of her in the Onassis Culture Foundation, in Athens.

Manto Mavrogenous, the Greek heroine of 1821. Today you can find a bust of Manto Mavrogenous in Pedion tou Areos, Athens.

Katina Paxinou, the first non-American woman winning an Oscar. Her Museum and Archive are housed in the Eynardos Mansion, 20 Agios Konstantinos St. and 52 Menandrou Street, in the centre of Athens.

Antigoni Metaxa-Krontira, the creator of Greek Children's Theatre. After her death she is commemorated in the park opposite the maternity hospital "Elena Venizelos" on a marble plaque.

Opi Zouni, a female Greek artist. Today, a lot of her paintings can be found in the Greek National Gallery in Athens.

Roza Imvrioti, the pioneer teacher. The school she founded is still named by her name to pay tribute to her contribution and work in the field of special education and can be found in Kaisariani, Athens.

Lela karagianni, the first Greek fighter against the Second World War. Today, there is a marble bust of her in Exarchia square in Athens. Also, her house and base of her resistance movement in Plateia Amerikis is considered to be a historical monument that needs special protection.

Kalliroi Paren, the first Greek Feminist. Today, a marble bust of her can be found in the 1st cemetery of Athens.

Melina Mercouri, the Greek Goddess. Today, there is a cultural foundation in her memorial that can be found in Polignotou 11, centre of Athens and a bust of her in Amalias Avenue and Dionysus Areopagitou in Plaka, Athens.

Tzeni Karezi, a talented actress. Today, there is the theater "Tzeni Karezi", named by her name. Also, in 1992 was created the foundation "Tzeni Karezi", that offers palliative care for free in cancer patients.

6.5. Sofia, Bulgaria

Female footprint in Sofia Sofia's history has been shaped by many remarkable women who have made significant contributions to the city and its development. Here are some historical female figures associated with Sofia.

Rayna Knyaginya (1856-1917). A teacher, maternity nurse, and revolutionary, famous for having sewn the flag of the April Uprising of 1876, which she waved together with other freedom fighters. As the uprising was brutally crushed by Ottoman troops, she was captured, raped, molested, and beaten for more than a month in prison. While receiving education abroad, she arranged the upbringing of 32 orphans from her hometown, including her younger brother, through a ladies' charity committee.

Ekaterina Karavelova (1860-1947). A well-known educator, translator, writer, publicist, suffragist, and women's rights activist. She also had an active role in protecting Bulgaria's Jewish population from deportation to concentration camps in WWII. Ekaterina was also the long-term chairwoman of the Union of Bulgarian Women Writers, created on her initiative. She represented Bulgaria at the 4th Congress of the International Women's League for Peace and Freedom in 1924 in Washington, USA. She was the founder of the cultural women's organisation Maika (Mother) and its chairperson in 1899-1929. Active as a teacher, Ekaterina was early on active in the debate of women's education and status of female teachers.

Elisaveta Bagryana (1893-1991). A prominent Bulgarian poet who lived in Sofia for much of her life. She is considered one of Bulgaria's most significant poets, often called "the first lady of Bulgarian women's literature". Elisaveta has been nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature three times and made substantial contributions to the country's literary heritage.

Yana Yazova (1912-1974). A writer and intellectual from the 20th century. Her poetry was translated into Esperanto, Czech, Serbian and Ukrainian. She travelled extensively in Europe and the Middle East and wrote about her travels as well. Her historical novel Alexander of Macedon, the trilogy Balkans and the anti-communist novel Salt Gulf were published after her death.

Mara Belcheva (1868-1937). A poet, teacher, translator, and philologist. She published three collections of poetry: "Footsteps on the Threshold", 1918, "Sonnets", 1926, and "Selected Songs", 1931. Mara published a biography of her late partner, poet Pencho Slaveykov, in 1925. She also translated Friedrich Nietzsche's *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* and Gerhart Hauptmann's *Die versunkene Glocke* into Bulgarian.

Anastasia Dimitrova (1815-1894). The first female teacher in Bulgaria. In 1839 she founded the first Bulgarian girls' school, thus laying the foundation of modern education in the country and conquering the place of women in education.

Anna Karima (1871-1949). Writer, translator, editor and journalist, suffragist and women's rights activist. In 1897 she founded the Women's Educational Association called "Conscious" through which Anna, with her constant letters to the government, managed to convince them to allow women to study in university in 1901. Anna also founded the Bulgarian Women's Union and organised the first congress of feminist organisations. Throughout her life she's constantly engaged in translating and writing own materials, all of them focused on feminine topics – from education of children, to opposing arranged marriages, to expressing freely one's emotions – her works challenge the traditional understandings at the time, combat stereotypes and influence the attitudes of women.

Elena Markova-Bosilkova (1894-1971). The first Bulgarian female architect.

Teodora Peykova (1892-1972). A writer, editor, and socialite, she founded the lady's magazine "Economy and household", which was published for 25 years. Through the magazine Teodora spread European taste and ideas throughout the country and used it to educate women about different social issues or inventions made by other women, to offer recipes and medical advice, weight-loss diets, press review, family advice, child-rearing advice, fashion, historical events, gymnastics, reports from Paris and other cities, advertisements, courses on sewing, embroideries, needlework, etc. She also became the first Bulgarian woman who taught herself how to drive her husband's car.

Konstantsa Lyapcheva (1887-1944). Socialite, involved in charity activities for unprivileged children (refugees, orphans, etc.). In the 1930s she was the first woman to actively engage with issues such as human trafficking, domestic violence, child protection. She was the

chairwoman of the Union for the Protection of Children of Bulgaria until the very end. She was a member of almost all other charitable organisations of Sofia, in many of them – as part of the management body. There is no area of social welfare in which she did not take part. Thanks to Konstanza, the activities of raising and educating children became the subject of law and received legislative protection, and motherhood was recognized as an extremely important social function. Upon her initiative, in 1927, June 1 was celebrated as Children's Day for the first time. She founded the first shelter homes for children in distress, for the training of social workers, summer camps and playgrounds.

Elisaveta Konsulova-Vazova (1881-1965). One of the first women professional artists in Bulgaria, the first Bulgarian woman to paint a nude figure at the State School of Painting and the first woman to host a solo exhibition. Elisaveta describes her revolutionary feminist ideas regarding child-rearing in a book about education – “Book for young mothers”. She is one of the founders of the Puppet Theater and the first editor-in-chief of the magazine "Home and World".

Elizaveta Karamihailova (1897-1968). The first female nuclear physicist in the country, she established the first practical courses of particle physics in Bulgaria and was the first woman to hold a professorial title in the country. Elizaveta graduated as a PhD in Physics and Mathematics in Vienna and was appointed as a docent of Experimental Atomistics with Radioactivity at Sofia University in 1939. She founded the radioactivity laboratory at the Physics Institute of the Bulgarian Science Academy.

It's important to note that some of the places, related to the women in this list, are no longer preserved or are not known in detail (with a specific location) due to the substantial lack of recorded female history. Despite their absence in history textbooks that further on creates the wrong impression that women have no contribution to the development of Bulgarian society, all these historical figures have left a lasting impact on Sofia's culture, politics, and intellectual life. Their accomplishments should continue to be remembered and celebrated in the city's history and heritage.

6.6. Velenje and Savinjsko-Šaleška region, Slovenia

During the desk research and focus groups the following female figures were identified.

In Velenje:

Jelka Reichman (1926-2017) was a Slovenian painter and illustrator who was born in Velenje. She is best known for her illustrations for children's books, many of which have become classics of Slovenian children's literature.

Zofka Kveder (1878-1926) was a writer and feminist who was born in Velenje. She was a pioneer of Slovenian feminist literature and was known for her novels, short stories, and essays.

Ljudmila Novak (born 1959) is a Slovenian politician who served as the mayor of Velenje from 1994 to 1998. She is also a former member of the Slovenian Parliament and served as the president of the Slovenian Democratic Party from 2000 to 2013.

Herma Groznik (1940-2022) Herma has been very active in shaping the local community throughout her life. She was a teacher who loved to be involved in many activities, but she had a special love for scouting and her contribution in this field was really great. Many would agree that it is to her credit that Scouting has become a part of all the primary schools in Velenje. In 2005, Hermina Groznik received a high municipal award - the coat of arms of the Municipality of Velenje - for her significant contribution to the local community.

Antonija Strnad (1873–1950) – midwife, helped to deliver around 4.000 babies during her professional life.

A miner's wife – fictional role.

In Celje:

Alma Karlin (1889-1950) was a Slovenian writer, traveller, and polyglot who was born in Celje. She travelled extensively throughout the world and wrote several books about her experiences, including "Globetrotting Through Siberia and Central Asia" and "In the Land of Silent People".

Franja Bojc Bidovec (1913-1944) was a Slovenian nurse who worked in a secret hospital in the mountains near Celje during World War II. She helped to care for wounded Partisan fighters and saved the lives of many people despite the constant threat of discovery and capture by the occupying forces.

Lili Novy (1885-1958) was a Slovenian poet, translator, and feminist who was born in Celje. She was a leading figure in Slovenian feminist literature and was known for her poems, essays, and translations of works by other writers.

These women, both known and lesser known, have left their mark in different areas of interest in Velenje and Celje, contributing to the cultural and intellectual heritage of their respective cities and the wider Slovenian society.

6.7. Vilnius, Lithuania

There are 2971 streets in Vilnius city, 42 out of them have forenames and surnames of honourable women or the names of female historical figures.³⁹ There are 715 commemorative plaques, sculptures, monuments and other artistic objects installed in Vilnius city. 377 of them are installed in memory of famous persons (some of them have a few commemorative objects in different places of the city). 22 commemorative plaques, sculptures and monuments are devoted to famous women (writers, artists, scientists, saviour of Jews, participants of resistance, grand duchess, etc.).

The following chapters briefly describe ten women who left their footprint in the history of Vilnius city, who were famous not only in Lithuania but also worldwide. All of them were active in the 20th century. Their memory is commemorated in various places of Vilnius city by the name of the streets, monuments, sculptures, and/or commemorative plaques.

Marija Alseikaitė-Gimbutienė (1921-1994). Lithuanian archaeologist, pioneer of archaeomythology of the 20th century. She cooperated in various archaeological publications and encyclopedias, participated in scientific conferences, wrote and published books on

³⁹ Retrieved from: <https://zemelapiai.vplanas.lt/vilniausdnr/en/streets>

archaeology and archaeomythology. She mainly studied post-Paleolithic Europe. A long-time lecturer, Professor.⁴⁰

Marija Horodničienė (1904-1975). Lithuanian ophthalmologist of the 20th century. She has done a lot in the field of treatment and prevention of blindness. A long-time lecturer at Vilnius University. In 1999 she received the Life Saviour's Cross Award.

Jurga Ivanauskaitė (1961-2007). Lithuanian writer, artist of the 20th – 21st centuries. She wrote a lot of novellas, novels, and non-fiction books. Also wrote poems, essays, books for children, illustrated books. Wrote articles on Tibetan freedom, religions, feminism, politics and other thematic.⁴¹

Marcelė Kubiliūtė (1898-1963). Lithuanian public figure, active in press, education and military areas. She is the only Lithuanian woman awarded all major Lithuanian orders.⁴²

Aldona Liobytė-Paškevičianė (1915-1985). Children's writer and translator from Vilnius. Her fairy tales, plays, and translations gave Lithuanian children the opportunity to discover both Lithuanian folk wisdom and classics of children's literature from around the world. This was the essence of her resistance to the Soviet occupation: in her works and translations Liobytė helped children to develop into smart, independent, and critically thinking adults.⁴³

Meilė Lukšienė (1913-2009). Literature researcher, pedagogue, educology expert. She was a member of the Lithuanian Reorganisation Movement "Sąjūdis" initiative group, and a pioneer of the Lithuanian educational reform, both nationally and internationally.⁴⁴

Ieva Simonaitytė (1897-1978). Writer; an author of autobiographic tales and novels, she depicted everyday life and exceptional destinies of "*lietuvinkai*" – Lithuanians from Lithuania Minor. She received critical acclaim for her novel *Aukštųjų Šimonių likimas* (The Fate of Šimoniai from Aukštieji, 1935).⁴⁵

⁴⁰ Retrieved from: <https://zemelapiai.vplanas.lt/vilniausdnr/en/persons/C12D2744-7EF5-40DA-B2EF-3742B05BA575>

⁴¹ Retrieved from: <https://zemelapiai.vplanas.lt/vilniausdnr/en/persons/6DC81B50-4E3B-4D7D-A0A6-EB6760A59BF2>

⁴² Retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marcel%C4%97_Kubili%C5%ABt%C4%97

⁴³ Retrieved from: <https://mokomesapie.lt/en/100/aldona-liobyte-classic-childrens-literature-and-the-resistance-can-fairy-tales-destroy-the-regime/>

⁴⁴ Retrieved from: https://ml100.ugdome.lt/?page_id=69

⁴⁵ Retrieved from: <http://antologija.lt/author/ieva-simonaityte?lang=en>

Šatrijos Ragana (1877-1930). Šatrijos Ragana, the pen name of Marija Pečkauskaitė, a Lithuanian humanist and romantic writer and educator. Pečkauskaitė was one of the first Lithuanian writers to create deep and complex characters, analysing not only their psychology but also spirituality. She also participated in the First Congress of Lithuanian Women and was elected its vice-chair.⁴⁶

Ona Šimaitė (1894-1970). Librarian at Vilnius University; used her position to aid and rescue Jews in the Vilnius ghetto. Entering the ghetto under the pretext of recovering library books from Jewish university students, she smuggled in food and other provisions and smuggled out literary and historical documents. In 1944, the Nazis arrested and tortured Šimaitė. She was then deported to Dachau and later transferred to a concentration camp in southern France. After the camp was liberated by the Allies, Šimaitė remained in France, working as a librarian, except for a period from 1953 to 1956 spent in Israel. On 15 March 1966, the Israeli organisation Yad Vashem recognized Šimaitė as a Righteous Among the Nations, planting a tree in her honour. Šimaitė died outside of Paris in 1970 and, per her request, her body was donated to science.⁴⁷

Eugenija Šimkūnaitė (1920-1996). Lithuanian pharmacist, herbalist, ethnographer, Habilitated Doctor of Biomedicine and Biology sciences of the 20th century. She was engaged in pharmacological activities, worked at the Institute of Biology, the Pharmaceutical Board of the Ministry of Health. Researched the habitats of medicinal plants, collected folklore, organised student herb gathering contests. Wrote books on medicinal plants, published scientific and science popularisation articles in various magazines.⁴⁸

6.8. Lecco, Italy

The city of Lecco, located in the Lombardy region, has a rich and fascinating history covering a long period of time. The dissemination of historical models in Lecco can take place through different initiatives and resources: museums and historical sites, thematic itineraries, cultural events and historical re-enactments, collaborations with schools and educational institutions,

⁴⁶ Retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/%C5%A0atrijos_Ragana

⁴⁷ Retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ona_%C5%A0imait%C4%97

⁴⁸ Retrieved from: <https://zemelapiai.vplanas.lt/vilniausdnr/en/persons/F560B367-4A2C-4120-A74D-2DCFD9E18A1D>

conservation and restoration projects, digital initiatives, art exhibitions and photographs. The goal is to create an environment in which Lecco's past is valued and appreciated as a precious resource for the present and future of the city.

The absence or limited representation of female figures in the history of Lombardy (and in history in general) is a common problem that reflects a broader historical tendency to underestimate or ignore the contributions of women. This phenomenon can be attributed to various factors, such as gender stereotypes, historically limited access to education and opportunities, and selective storytelling.

Therefore, in the specific territory of Valle San Martino and the province of Lecco, which is the subject of this research, there is a complete lack of knowledge regarding local female figures. This absence is also reflected in a widespread lack of streets, monuments, squares, and buildings dedicated to women.

However, through in-depth research, women have emerged who, at different historical moments, have contributed to the creation of Lecco's history. Among them are the following.

Antonia Pozzi (1912-1938). A poet and writer who, through her works, conveyed her love for nature and Lake Como.

Antonietta Nava (1912-2005). A teacher and school principal for 46 years; she also served as vice mayor and city councilor.

Elena Gandolfi (1945-2003). A language teacher and researcher in international adoptions, who published some research. As president of the Ciai (Italian Center for International Adoptions), she worked nationally and internationally to promote bilateral agreements between governments and improve adoption legislation.

Piera Badoni (1912-1989). A poet with a strong connection to the city of Lecco, who was associated with prominent Italian literary and intellectual figures.

Carla Acquistapace (1918-2008). A member of the Communist Party, actively involved in distributing anti-fascist propaganda and clandestine press materials through Women's Defense Groups.

Zaira Spreafico (1920-2004). She served as a volunteer Red Cross nurse in military hospitals and dedicated herself to the "Opera di don Luigi Monza," caring for abandoned children after the war, orphans, and children of executed and political prisoners.

Gabriella Zanini (1921-2010). She established the first service for terminally ill cancer patients in the Lecco area, founding the ACMT association dedicated to providing care for terminally ill patients.

Despite the research highlighting the presence of historical female figures who left their mark on the Lecco territory, there are no streets, roads, squares, or monuments dedicated to them. Moreover, the local citizens are unaware of the existence of these women, and when asked to think of historical female figures from Lecco, only Lucia Mondella, a fictional character from Alessandro Manzoni's historical novel "I Promessi Sposi" (The Betrothed), set in the Lecco territory, is mentioned.

7. Local Strategies around European Cities

7.1. Spain

Regarding local strategies for the promotion of women's history, the Municipal Institute of Education of Salamanca City Council has created a support booklet to learn about the history of the Women of Salamanca and a map of routes where these women are located, whether in streets, monuments or squares.

In addition, the Salamanca City Council has implemented different workshops for the promotion of Women in the History of Salamanca, highlighting content such as Vaccean women among invading armies, Women among Monarchs: Queens, consorts, princesses and lovers, University Women: Beatriz de Galindo, Lucía de Medrano, Teresa de Jesús, Dolores Cebrián, Feliciano Enríquez, Carmen Martín Gaité, Matilde Cherner and Women in the medallions of the Plaza de Salamanca.

The Salamanca City Council, in collaboration with Turismo de Salamanca, is organizing a series of guided tours throughout May. These are free visits to highlight the relevant role of some of the women in the history and heritage of the city, which they call "Salamanca with a woman's voice", this visit is carried out to give visibility to the relevant women in the history of Salamanca, from the Casa de la Mujer Clara Campoamor and its School of Equality.

The Salamanca City Council's website also provides accessible information about important figures in the city, such as Saint Teresa of Jesus (<https://salamanca.es/es/productos-turisticos/huellas-de-teresa>). The organisation organises competitions to make women more visible, such as the "For Equality" Graffiti and Mural Painting Competition (<http://www.familiaeigualdad.aytosalamanca.es/es/mujer/concursosycertamenes/concurso/Graffitis.html>).

On the other hand, the opening of the Casa de la Mujer "Clara Campoamor" by the City Council shows its priority in the fight for equality and the rights of all women.

Likewise, different routes can be found in the Salamanca Tourist Office, including the Huella de Santa Teresa, a woman who has contributed to the history of Salamanca, with her enterprising spirit, literary quality, spirituality and reformist values.

In Salamanca, several exhibitions have been held, such as the one exhibited in the Torrente Ballester Municipal Library on 10 and 29 May 2020 called "Women who change history" by the artist Pilar Vega Pérez, by means of a collage with the faces of 37 women fighters, artists, vindicators, avant-garde, pioneers and forgotten women.

Likewise, the University of Salamanca, the City Council, the Junta de Castilla y León and the associations IDArte y Mujeres dos Rombos presented the project "Rostros del Olvido", a project that makes visible those women who studied at the University of Salamanca throughout its history and did important work, but were unjustly left in the shadows.

At the level of the community of Castilla y León, there are various associations that, in the common interest of women, organise themselves to make the work of women in the community visible, such as the association APFCyL, which is in charge of making women visible in the media of Castilla y León.

7.2. France (Martinique)

In Martinique, several historians and organisations are working with the aim of disseminating gender balanced history. For example, L'Union des Femmes de Martinique (UFM), the first feminist organisation in the Caribbean, founded by Jane Léro. Initially, it was a local extension of the Union des Femmes Françaises, a movement initiated by women resistance fighters during the Second World War. Today, UFM's mission is to defend and promote women's rights to build a society of equality between women and men in Martinique. Among other things, UFM works to raise awareness about women in the history of Martinique and, more broadly, in the Caribbean and the world, because, as they explain, they are "convinced that history is essential for understanding ourselves, and even more so, the knowledge of women's history". To do this, they work on the valorisation of a whole series of women, such as the "charbonnières" (charcoal workers) of Fort-de-France, or those who have carried various causes within social movements. UFM also offers several traveling exhibitions and workshops

aimed at the general public. This very short, dynamic format is a first approach that raises awareness of social representations, misunderstood realities, clarifies certain concepts, etc. The association also offers training courses to help raise awareness and develop skills.

There is also LimièKilti, a cultural organisation offering services combining history, culture and digital for public and/or private professionals. Mélody MOUTAMALLE, the founder, is currently working on an insertion project involving history, heritage, and art. She has also participated in the creation of tourist circuits, murals, and exhibitions. A chronological timeline of Martinique's history has also been created, and she would like to do the same but in the form of mini thematic timelines (on women's history, on the history of social movements, etc.).

Culture Égalité (CE), is a feminist association based in Martinique which contributes to building a society based on gender equality, diversity, and solidarity. The association is aimed at all women, helping them to defend their rights and to be free, independent, and united. Among their objectives, there is the desire to make visible the heritage of women and their contribution to the social, political, economic, and cultural development of our society.

Other personalities, organisations and historians are also keen to help valorize women in history and promote gender equality.

7.3. Cyprus

The local community in Nicosia, Cyprus, takes various approaches to preserve and share its history, including maintaining heritage sites, conducting historical tours, and organizing cultural events. However, a closer examination reveals a lack of representation of women in these historical narratives. It is worth exploring the stories of women associated with these places. For instance, Maria Iacovou, a professor of archaeology at the University of Cyprus, has significantly enhanced our understanding of ancient Cyprus, showcasing the potential of such explorations.

Nicosia hosts significant cultural institutions, such as the Leventis Municipal Museum of Nicosia and the Cyprus Museum. These establishments play a crucial role in safeguarding and

disseminating the city's history. However, there is a need to assess how they portray the contributions of women in this historical narrative.

Nicosia boasts a diverse collection of historical and cultural sites that weave together the city's rich past. Notable landmarks like the Venetian Walls, Famagusta Gate, and the Archbishop's Palace serve as tangible reminders of Nicosia's history. Nonetheless, these landmarks often feature stories that disproportionately center around male figures, leaving women's contributions in the background.

Consider Maria Iacovou, an archaeology professor at the University of Cyprus. Her work has significantly expanded our knowledge of ancient Cyprus. However, how well-known are her achievements among Nicosia residents and visitors? How frequently are her contributions showcased in tours or exhibitions? While these landmarks offer insights into the city's history, they can unintentionally perpetuate a limited, gender-biased perspective if they fail to include women's stories.

Addressing this imbalance necessitates reevaluating the methods employed to promote Nicosia's history. This might involve designing guided tours that emphasize women's contributions or organizing exhibitions dedicated specifically to women's roles in Nicosia's history. These strategies could contribute to a more balanced gender representation of the city's historical narrative and thus, empower girls and women towards gender equality.

When implementing these measures, it is crucial for them to garner appropriate visibility. In particular, it is essential for local residents to learn about Cyprus's history. Additionally, when new historical findings emerge, disseminating them through mass media channels can ensure widespread awareness and recognition, ultimately acknowledging the efforts of diligent individuals. The presence of women in these significant positions should serve as an inspiring example to be emulated across various fields.

7.4. Greece

Greece and its capital Athens, has a rich history that dates back thousands of years and is accessible to all citizens up to today. Various archaeological sites and museums are located at the city center, such as the Acropolis, the National Archaeological Museum, the Acropolis

Museum etc. Also, the dissemination of history includes guided tours by experts- guides who provide insights into the significance and stories behind each location. Very important are also the private and public cultural institutions like the Byzantine and Christian Museum and the Benaki Museum, that exhibit historical artifacts and artworks relevant to the city's history. Finally, there are various digital platforms in Greece and Athens, to disseminate historical information of different periods of time and geographical areas. Online archives, virtual tours, and interactive websites allow people from all over the world to explore Greek and Athenian history.

Specifically, at a regional level, and according to the local history of each area in Greece, municipalities are organizing events and festivals to celebrate historical anniversaries, and the contributions or sacrifices of local people. However, women's contributions and perspectives have often been underrepresented in traditional historical narratives, so most events and festivals don't include the gender perspective. When these celebrations are about women, they are mostly dedicated to the tremendous sacrifices and fights of women, during the Greek War of Independence (1821) or the Second World War. It seems that despite the rich history of Greece and the variety of historical spots and museums, there is not an established and specific strategy for the promotion of equal gender representation in history. Most often the representation of women lays on the initiative of local institutions, organisations and stakeholders.

Despite this situation, a lot of steps have been taken recently to improve gender equality, something that is often being promoted through gender representation in history. Municipalities are obliged to have gender equality committees that act towards that direction. Recently, Municipality of Dirfya- Messapia in Evia took such a step by organizing an event dedicated to women that changed modern history with their work⁴⁹. Museums, historical sites, and cultural institutions in Greece have made efforts to include exhibitions and displays that highlight the contributions of women throughout history, in various fields, such as politics, art, science, and social movements.

⁴⁹ Retrieved from: <https://eviaportal.gr/pragmatopoiithike-ekdilosi-gynaikes-pou-echoun-allaksei-syghroni-istoria/>

7.5. Bulgaria

No public information on local strategies for promoting gender balanced history was found for the purpose of this report. Topics of “gender” or “women” are absent from the school curriculum for high school students. These topics are also absent in municipal strategic action plans and strategic development plans.

Moreover, the term “gender” entered Bulgarian language with a negative connotation, primarily due to the targeted right-wing rhetoric against the Istanbul Convention that led to a misconception of the term for the general public. In 2018 Bulgaria became the first country that refused to ratify the document and set a dangerous precedent by its inaction towards women in risk. The topic is still relevant nowadays, especially considering the rising number of cases of gender-based violence in the country in the past years.

7.6. Slovenia

The practices in disseminating gender balanced history are very limited. The initiative to disseminate a gender-balanced history is informed by the challenges in researching and acknowledging women's historical contributions, stemming from a lack of documentation and narratives. The stark underrepresentation of women in the city's street names has been one of the concerns, prompting efforts to propose female names.

There is a need to emphasize the pivotal role of women, particularly mining women, in Velenje's history, advocating for the acknowledgment and celebration of their contributions. Addressing the historical gender bias is crucial, and educational initiatives should be implemented to bridge the knowledge gap, ensuring that the stories of both men and women are equally celebrated and remembered in Velenje's historical narrative.

In Velenje, the city has a strong focus on promoting the history of the city and its industrial heritage. The city's practices in disseminating history patterns include the Velenje Museum, which showcases the history of the city and its mining industry, and the Velenje Castle, which houses a museum of local history. The city also hosts regular cultural and historical events, including the Velenje Festival, which features a range of cultural and artistic events, and the Festival of Industrial Heritage, which celebrates the city's industrial past.

The neighbouring city Celje has a more diverse approach to disseminating history patterns. While the city also has a strong focus on promoting its history, it also emphasizes the importance of cultural heritage and art. The city's practices in disseminating history patterns include the Celje Regional Museum, which showcases the history of the city and the wider region, and the Celje Gallery of Contemporary Art, which features exhibitions of contemporary art. The city also hosts regular cultural events, including the Celje International Children's Festival and the Days of Poetry and Wine, which celebrate poetry and wine from the region.

If women were previously neglected when depicting the important milestones in the town's history, that is not the case at present. In Velenje, there are several women who have been awarded a plaque by the municipality of Velenje for their contribution to improving the lives of the citizens. For example, the Curator of the Year, who tried to introduce artistic culture to Velenje, the Scout woman, who developed the mentality of scouting in Velenje, the politicians who have been ministers, and of course many sportswomen. Every year Velenje also hosts the largest children's festival, dedicated to a girl (albeit fictitious) called "Pikin festival" (Pippi Långstrump), which emphasises that women are capable of anything they desire.

7.7. Lithuania

Information on practises in disseminating gender balanced history in Vilnius is fragmented due to the large autonomy of Lithuanian municipal administrations and other entities in carrying out educational and/or cultural initiatives. Public institutions set up by the municipal administrations (such as public schools, libraries, museums, cultural centres, etc.) may independently pursue local small-scale initiatives to promote gender balanced history, for example, organise exhibitions, public lectures, tours, and other activities. This is also supported by private efforts and initiatives.

Recently there is a notable increase of exhibitions devoted to famous women, their work and input into Lithuanian history. For instance, an exhibition for Lithuanian born artist Aleksandra Kasuba or special exhibition "Women warriors"⁵⁰ telling the stories of women warriors of the

⁵⁰ Retrieved from: <https://lnm.lt/renginiai/kovoju-siu-moteru-istorijos-parodoje-kovotojos-xix-xx/>

19th and 20th centuries. In addition, guided tours about prominent women who lived in Vilnius are becoming increasingly popular.⁵¹ Among many European capitals Vilnius stands out as the city celebrating national Emancipation Day. Each year, on 17 February, right after the celebration of the national Independence Day on the 16th, an alternative highly symbolic celebration is organised commemorating a rally held in Kaunas on this day in 1918 to protest against the exclusion of women among the signatories of Lithuanian independence.⁵²

Regarding local strategies, there is no publicly available information on local strategies of promoting gender balanced history. Topics of “gender” or “women” are absent from the national history curriculum for the high-school students. These topics are also absent in municipal strategic action plans and strategic development plans.

7.8. Italy

The growing desire for concrete action towards effective change, in 2022, the city of Lecco promoted an initiative. On the month hosting International Women's Rights Day, the Municipality proposed to dedicate its civic halls to female figures linked to the history of the city and the territory. To do this, the City Administration opened a survey addressed to citizens, allowing them to express their preferences among nine important women.

The decision to dedicate the city's civic halls to symbolic women of the territory aimed to recognize the value of female leadership. Civic halls were chosen because they represent places of participation; hence the commitment to promote and strengthen the role of women as protagonists.

The initiative sought to acknowledge and celebrate the historical contributions of women in the local community and to increase their visibility and representation in public spaces. By naming the civic halls after these significant women, the city aimed to honour their legacy and inspire current and future generations with their stories of achievements and impact.

⁵¹ Gasiulytė, E. (2018). *History's forgotten Vilnius women would now be Instagram stars*. Retrieved from: <https://madeinvilnius.lt/vilniaus-istorija/vilniaus-miesto-studija/istorijos-pamirstos-vilniaus-moterys-dabar-butu-instagram-zvaigzdemis/>

⁵² Lithuanian National Radio and Television. (2022). 17 February is National Emancipation Day: Manifesto read in Vilnius, calling for ratification of the Istanbul Convention. Retrieved from: <https://www.lrt.lt/mediateka/irasas/2000201449/vasario-17-oji-nacionaline-emancipacijos-diena-vilniuje-skaitytas-manifestas-raginta-ratifikuoti-stambulo-konvencija>

As early as 2020, the youth of AmbientalMente, a civic political project in Lecco focusing on environmental and social sustainability, gave voice to the gender equality issue through an innovative action. The young people symbolically changed the names of three streets in the city, dedicating them to three prominent women from the history of our country. This initiative aimed to underline the importance of gender equality and the fundamental role of women, which unfortunately is often underestimated or forgotten even in Lecco.

Looking at the city's streets, a book titled "Lecco, il significato delle vie dalla A alla Z" (Lecco, the meaning of the streets from A to Z) reveals that out of all the streets, 233 are named after men (including 18 characters from "I Promessi Sposi" - "The Betrothed") and only eleven streets are dedicated to female figures (including 6 characters from "I Promessi Sposi"). Through a survey, citizens were invited to choose three women from a list of ten important female figures. The results were as follows:

- 3rd place - Nilde Iotti, President of the Chamber of Deputies (1920-1999)
- 2nd place - Francesca (Vera) Ciceri, anti-fascist and partisan from Lecco (1904-1988)
- 1st place - Lea Garofalo, mafia victim (1974-2009)

Through a flash mob, the young people of AmbientalMente displayed new street signs alongside the original ones, bearing the names of Lea Garofalo, Vera Ciceri, and Nilde Iotti. This was a way to emphasize the value given to the concept of social sustainability, translated in this context into gender equality.

8. Transnational level conclusions

The national reports developed by the partners revealed that progress has been made in gender equality, however, there are still needs that need to be addressed. The progress that has been made concludes a combination of actions, such as the establishment of laws and institutions promoting gender equality in different countries. Together with the institutionalised actions, it is crucial to enhance gender equality by promoting gender female visibility in all sectors of society.

Furthermore, it is a common truth that all partner countries have faced a lot of societal changes in the field of gender equality although there is still a long way to go until European cities can be fully diverse and gender-inclusive in all fields of life.

The analysis of the Desk Research indicates that the number of known female figures around European cities is proportionally smaller when compared to the number of known male figures. The most common result is that women were not absent from remarkable times in history and also in contemporary history, rather than marginalised from the dominant narrative.

This was confirmed throughout the Focus Groups conducted by all partners with local stakeholders who stated the difficulties they faced in finding remarkable female footprints in history. Stakeholders' contribution was definitive since they mentioned crucial information about remarkable accomplishments of female figures. On the other hand, the Focus Groups with young people confirmed the consortium's outlooks. The consortium, taking in mind the gender misrepresentation in history and the marginalisation of half of the population in different aspects of life, expected that young people would have little knowledge about female presence in history.

Even though the National Reports indicate several difficulties and challenges in all partner countries, in conclusion, there is a common point when it comes to the results of the Focus Groups with young people. Young people have a large interest in learning more about female figures in history. Thus, the consortium detects potentials in promoting gender equality by empowering young people and by changing the dominant narrative and the dominant gender roles by developing initiatives such as the HerStory project.